

Deliverable 3.2

Report on successes & Failures of Empowerment based on Q-method and perceptions of Ocean Literacy across the host countries 1.0

26 September 2025

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PUBLIC

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101059957 (EmpowerUs). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participants in EmpowerUs are supported by UKRI Grant No. 10040189 (QUB).

Document Information

Grant Agreement	101059957
Project Acronym	EmpowerUs
Project Title	Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development

Deliverable Number	D3.2
Work Package Number	WP3
Deliverable Title	Report on successes & Failures of Empowerment based on Q-method and perceptions of Ocean Literacy across the host countries
Lead Beneficiary	NRI, Partner Number 1
Author(s)	Salina Spiering, Julien Lebel, Cecilie Bratt, Maiken Bjørkan, Anette Møllersen Bjørna, Vida Steiro, Nordland Research Institute Anna Antonova, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München Gloriya Marinova, Diyana Kostovska, Radostina Tsenova, Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation Maria Hadjimichael, Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute, Cyprus Kristina Svells, Natural Resources Institute Viktor Eriksson, The Fisheries Agency at the Government of Åland Brendan Murtagh, Wesley Flannery, Alex Miller, Queen's University Belfast Silvia Gómez Mestres, Beatriz Patraca Dibildox, and Miroslav Pulgar Corrotea Autonomous University of Barcelona
Due Date	30.09.2025
Submission Date	26.09.2025
Dissemination Level	PU ¹
Type of Deliverable	R ²

Version 0.1 First Draft Q-results	08.04.2024, Spiering S., Bjørkan M., Bratt C. (NRI) & TCLs
Version 0.2 Reviewed by Project Coordinator & consortium partners	01.09.2025, Spiering S., Lebel J., et al.
Version 1.0 Final Version	25.09.2025 Spiering S., Lebel J., et al.

Suggested citation: Spiering, S., Lebel, J., Bjørkan, M., Bratt, C., Bjørna, A. M., Steiro, V., Nordland Research Institute, Antonova, A., Marinova, G., Kostovska, D., Tsenova, R., Hadjimichael, M., Svells, K., Eriksson, V., Murtagh, B., Flannery, W., Miller, A., Gómez Mestres, S., Patraca Dibildox, B., & Pulgar Corrotea, M. (2025). Report on successes & Failures of Empowerment based on Q-method and perceptions of Ocean Literacy across the host countries (EmpowerUs Deliverable 3.2) [Report]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17182577>

¹ Dissemination level: **PU**: Public, information as referred to in European Commission Decision 2015/844

² Type of deliverable: **R**: **Document**, Report

Executive Summary

Coastal communities across Europe are navigating challenges and opportunities related to local development, demographic change, resource management, social inclusion, cultural identity, and sustainability. EmpowerUs activities, carried out in six Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) in Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Norway, and Spain, supported the socio-economic empowerment of these communities by bringing together stakeholders, stimulating knowledge exchange, raising awareness, testing practical tools, and strengthening cooperation. These activities were embedded in broader Tailored Empowerment Programs (TEPs) designed to reflect the needs and contexts of each community. A TEP draws on social, economic, and cultural practices as well as inclusive, participatory processes to move from niche-level initiatives to broader transformations, aiming to re-direct the Blue Economy to support thriving coastal communities and advance Blue Justice.

This report evaluates perceived changes in empowerment in each TCL in connection with EmpowerUs activities. The Blue Justice framework constitutes the backbone of the analysis, with empowerment understood as a process of “gaining capacity” across three dimensions: access to resources and institutions, strategies for mobilising them, and the willingness to act. Two surveys capture change: the baseline survey (using Q-methodology) captured different viewpoints within each community at the project’s outset, while the evaluation survey (Likert-scale questions and qualitative interviews) assessed empowerment towards its conclusion. Comparing both surveys traced shifts in empowerment over time and identified persistent barriers.

Findings highlight participants’ willingness to contribute to sustainable development and to put ideas into practice. EmpowerUs activities strengthened connections to the local environment, increased recognition of community assets, and improved dialogue within and across stakeholder groups. However, access to resources remains limited, influence on higher-level decision-making is weak, and benefits from the blue economy are often perceived as unfair. While local empowerment improved, these structural barriers hinder longer-term impacts. Differences across the TCLs underline the importance of place-based contexts, yet common patterns emerge: coastal actors feel more empowered locally, but less able to influence decisions at regional, national, or EU levels.

Interviews emphasise that building trust and sustained dialogue between communities, stakeholders, and policymakers is essential. Such dialogue fosters knowledge sharing, enhances understanding of governance dynamics, and increases the potential for fairer decision-making. The report also draws on results from a national-level ocean literacy survey that included empowerment questions, using these findings to contextualise and reinforce TCL-level trends. While empowerment is inherently complex to evaluate—particularly over a short timeframe—the report underlines that it should be seen as a continuous, context-dependent process shaped by the lived experiences and perceptions of local stakeholders.

The report concludes with key lessons for policy and practice:

- Empowerment requires sustained investment in access to resources, fairer distribution of benefits, and opportunities to influence decisions beyond the local level.
- Tailored, context-sensitive approaches (such as TEPs) are more effective than “one-size-fits-all” solutions.
- Recognising cultural identities, traditional practices, and environmental stewardship as assets strengthens community resilience.
- Creating genuine spaces for dialogue across governance levels is critical to achieving Blue Justice and supporting long-term coastal sustainability.

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1 Introduction

This report presents the evaluation results of the Tailored Empowerment Programs (TEPs) developed and implemented in the six EmpowerUs Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) located in Bulgaria (Burgas), Cyprus (Eastern Limassol Region), Finland (Åland), Ireland (Connemara and the Aran Islands), Norway (Træna), and Spain (Cap de Creus) (Figure 1). EmpowerUs aims to support the socio-economic empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea, thereby promoting sustainable coastal development. As defined in D.4.2 Annex (EmpowerUs Deliverable 4.2 Annex), a TEP draws on social, economic, and cultural practices as well as inclusive, participatory, and bottom-up processes to move from niche-level initiatives to broader niche-to-niche regime transformations, ultimately aiming to achieve a common vision—i.e., re-directing the Blue Economy to support thriving coastal communities and advance Blue Justice. To achieve this in practice, TEPs were designed as sustainability transition pathways tailored to the specific needs of each TCL. These programs enable communities to build a sustainable future through planned actions and a combination of empowerment tools, both in the short term (via pilot implementations, ocean literacy activities, and other interventions during the project) and in the long term (beyond the project’s duration).

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, EmpowerUs initially planned to assess empowerment through a baseline and follow-up Q-method survey. While the baseline Q-survey was completed, the follow-up survey was not implemented. Instead, we adopted a context-sensitive approach: a mixed-method evaluation survey combining quantitative and qualitative components, co-designed with academic leads in each TCL to ensure local relevance, accessibility across languages, and broader inclusivity. This methodological adaptation allowed for a richer understanding of empowerment changes and reflected local contexts, rather than constituting a limitation.

The evaluation builds on two main surveys. The baseline Q-survey, conducted at the project’s outset, established an initial understanding of empowerment perceptions, identified local empowerment needs, and informed the design of pilots in each TCL. The evaluation survey, conducted toward the project’s conclusion, combined Likert-scale questions and qualitative interviews to assess changes in empowerment following interventions such as workshops, pilot implementations, and ocean literacy activities. This survey replaced the originally planned second Q-survey and allowed for a comparable assessment of change while incorporating additional qualitative insights. Both surveys were developed and administered in close collaboration with local academic leads in each TCL to ensure local relevance and allow participation across language barriers. The report also draws on results from a national-level ocean literacy survey that included empowerment questions, using these findings to contextualize and reinforce TCL-level trends. Most of the ocean literacy survey results are reported in D6.3 (Report on TCL Ocean Literacy Activities and Blue Justice Stories), whereas this deliverable (D3.2) focuses on linking these findings to empowerment at the local TCL level and interpreting changes over the course of the project.

In addition, the survey results feed into the WP5 Roadmap to Inclusive & Just Coastal Community Transitions (see EmpowerUs Deliverable 5.1). The Roadmap is structured around a “stepping-stone” model, where each stone marks a stage in the co-creation process and the leaps between them are moments of reflexive questioning. From this study, guidance material on the use of the Q-method is made accessible within the Roadmap, including EmpowerUs’ novel “Blue Q” – a framework combining empowerment theory, the Q-method, and Blue Justice dimensions – as a practical example of how project innovations can inform future coastal transition initiatives.

Figure 1 Map of Europe showing the six TCLs in EmpowerUs.

The report first clarifies the theoretical frameworks used to operationalise empowerment and describes the applied methods. It then presents the results of the baseline and evaluation surveys, followed by a discussion of factors that positively influenced empowerment perceptions as well as barriers—institutional, financial, technological, and cultural—that remained unchanged. Some questions in the evaluation survey (D3.2) overlap with the national ocean literacy survey (D6.3), allowing TCL-level and national-level responses to be compared and emerging trends in empowerment perceptions to be highlighted. The report concludes with key insights and recommendations, aimed at supporting future coastal transition initiatives, strengthening empowerment practices, and informing policymakers and practitioners engaged in coastal governance.

2 Analytical framework

Our methodology and analyses are based on different concepts that are relevant to study societal changes in coastal communities (see Figure 2). Our theoretical framework for analysing empowerment in coastal community transitions adopts Avelino's (2017: 8) original definition of empowerment as "the process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal." This process of "gaining capacity" is further explained through three interrelated dimensions: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies for mobilising these resources, and (3) the willingness to do so. Empowerment thus emerges as actors not only obtain access and develop strategies, but also actively choose to engage, emphasizing intrinsic motivation—where motivation

arises from positive, self-generated experiences rather than external rewards or supervision. The extent to which individuals feel empowered depends on their cognitive assessment of activities in terms of their meaningfulness, competence, impact, and choice (Avelino 2017: 512).

Key Concepts

EMPOWERMENT

The process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal (Avelino 2017)

- Access to resources and institutions
- Strategies for mobilising these resources
- Willingness to do so

BLUE JUSTICE FRAMEWORK

Framing empowerment through social justice dimensions relevant to coastal contexts (Bennett et al. 2021)

- **Recognitional justice**
Knowledge about accessing institutions and governance arrangements
- **Procedural justice**
Ability to participate meaningfully in decision-making
- **Distributional justice**
Ability to rely on fair resolution

POWER IN TRANSITION FRAMEWORK

Three forms of power are central to sustainability transitions (Avelino 2017)

- **Landscape**
Values, worldviews, institutions, macro-political/economic trends
 - **Regime**
Dominant practices, governance, rules and stability
 - **Niche**
Local innovations, pilots, grassroots experiments
- ← *Reinforcive power*
Maintaining existing institutions
- ← *Innovative power*
Creating new resources and ideas that challenge dominant systems
- ← *Transformative power*
Reshaping structures and institutions toward systemic change

Julien Lebel, Norelandslorsring AS, 2020

Figure 2 Summary of key concepts used in the methodology and analyses.

To operationalise empowerment in EmpowerUs, we apply the Blue Justice framework (Bennett et al. 2021), which frames empowerment through social justice dimensions relevant to coastal contexts. This framework highlights three key aspects:

- **Recognitional justice**, or the extent to which communities have knowledge about accessing institutions and governance arrangements.
- **Procedural justice**, the ability to participate meaningfully in decision-making; and
- **Distributional justice**, their ability to rely on fair resolution.

Recognizing empowerment as a contested and dynamic process, Blue Justice serves as a flexible tool rather than a fixed checklist, enabling comparative analysis across EmpowerUs' six diverse coastal communities. This approach draws on literature originating from small-scale fisheries debates (Isaacs 2019, Kerezi et al. 2020, Jentoft et al. 2022) and builds on the advocacy work of the Too Big to Ignore network, which ties social justice to environmental and climate justice concerns (Isaacs 2012, Blythe et al. 2023). According to Blythe et al. (2023: 3), Blue Justice "refers to the recognition, meaningful involvement and fair treatment of all coastal people with respect to how ocean and coastal resources are accessed, used, managed and enjoyed". For EmpowerUs, the Blue Justice concept is put to work as a means to assess empowerment through the lens of social justice in blue contexts. Building on this, we developed "Blue Q" – a practical framework combining empowerment theory, Q-methodology,

and Blue Justice dimensions – which is presented in the WP5 Roadmap (EmpowerUs Deliverable 5.1) as guidance for applying these concepts in future coastal transition initiatives.

Complementing this, the **Power in Transition framework** (Avelino 2017) distinguishes three forms of power central to sustainability transitions:

- **Reinforcive power**, maintaining existing institutions;
- **Innovative power**, creating new resources and ideas that challenge dominant systems; and
- **Transformative power**, reshaping structures and institutions toward systemic change.

Power is understood as relational and enacted by actors, with empowerment involving critical reflection on unintended disempowering effects that can emerge in transition efforts.

Within EmpowerUs, TCLs function as niches to foster innovative power through locally tailored solutions. These niches interact with dominant regimes and macro trends, potentially driving transformative change. Reinforcive power is not merely obstructive but can support the embedding of innovations into existing governance structures. Each TCL navigates these power dynamics uniquely, aiming to scale successful niche innovations into new niche-regime pathways. For the evaluation study, we applied this framework as an analytical lens to examine how EmpowerUs engaged with niche, regime, and landscape levels, and to identify the ways in which different forms of power were activated across contexts. This integrated framework supports a nuanced analysis of empowerment as a multifaceted, evolving process, attentive to justice dimensions and power relations across different levels, crucial for understanding and facilitating sustainable transitions in coastal communities.

3 Methodology

3.1 Baseline survey - Q-Methodology

To gain insight into the perspectives of local stakeholders across the six TCLs regarding their perceptions of empowerment, we employed the Q methodology (Stephenson 1935). Q methodology is a mixed research approach that blends qualitative and quantitative methods to explore diverse views within a group. It is particularly useful for examining complex or contested issues where people may hold very different opinions (Watts and Stenner 2012). The Q sorting results can reveal patterns by showing intersubjective arrangements of shared beliefs among people. These patterns indicate the degree of similarity or dissimilarity in individual perspectives. The Q-sort analysis reduces unique viewpoints to a few concise and general perspectives, which emerge from the quantitative Factor analysis as so-called “Factors” (these Factors, or “perspectives,” can be used interchangeably to describe the shared viewpoints identified). These Factors are then supplemented and contextualised by qualitative information from interviews. The analysis uncovers patterns within and between individuals, but it does not measure the distribution of beliefs across characteristics or categories in a population (Curry et al. 2013). The goal of this approach is to identify the main viewpoints that exist within a group, reveal how people’s perspectives overlap or differ, and provide a structured way of comparing them.

The first phase of a Q methodology implies defining a precise research question and designing a set of statements (often referred to as “Q statements”). Then, participants are requested to review all Q statements and place them on a grid, ranking them from “most agree” to “most disagree” in relation to the research question. The grid illustrates different levels of agreement and disagreement, and each Q statement must be placed by the participants themselves according to their own opinions.

Importantly, each tile of the grid must be filled, and two statements cannot be placed on the same tile, obliging participants to hierarchise all the Q statements (forced distribution). The vertical ranking of Q statements has, however, no meaning for the analysis (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Empty grid used in the Q methodology for the baseline survey.

One advantage of Q methodology is that it allows all participants to engage with the same set of statements, making their responses directly comparable. At the same time, it captures the richness of individual perspectives and highlights patterns across the group (Brown 1993, Webler et al. 2009, Watts and Stenner 2012).

To establish a baseline understanding of how people in the six EmpowerUs TCLs perceive empowerment, the Blue-Q survey – EmpowerUs’ tailored Q-methodology framework combining empowerment theory and Blue Justice dimensions – was conducted between months 6 and 16 of the project. They sorted Q statements on Blue Justice and empowerment according to their beliefs, indicating agreement or disagreement with each statement (ibid.).

The study followed three main steps:

1. Developing Blue-Q statements and identifying participants in each TCL
2. Conducting Blue-Q-sorting exercises
3. Analysing the quantitative and qualitative results (involving statement sorting and qualitative reasoning).

3.1.1 Development of statements and identification of participants in each TCL

The Q methodology initiates by defining the so-called “concourse”, capturing all relevant discussions on the topic—here, Blue Justice aspects in coastal communities—to illuminate stakeholder perspectives. In EmpowerUs, this process integrated various structured and unstructured sources, such as academic literature review, exploratory interviews, and discussions within TCLs. Collaborating with academic leads and hosts from six EmpowerUs TCL areas, we curated a Q-set of 13 statements (the Blue Q). These statements, drawn from the Blue Justice Framework, encompass recognitional, procedural, distributional justice, and environmental aspects, tailored to resonate with diverse stakeholders. Derived initially from 15 recognitional, 8 procedural, 21 distributional justice statements, and 4 environmental aspects, the set underwent refinement with input from TCL partners, resulting in 13 finalised statements. These were categorised into recognitional (1-4), procedural (5-8), and distributional justice (9-12), with Statement 13 addressing location-specific issues provocatively. The Blue Q-set, developed in English, was translated and presented in multiple languages—Norwegian, Swedish, Spanish/Catalan, Bulgarian, Greek (Cyprus), —to ensure inclusivity. In TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland), the statements were not translated into Irish, but information was provided in English. Table 1 showcases the Blue Q-set used in our study.

Table 1 Blue Q set applied in the six EmpowerUs TCLs.

RECOGNITIONAL JUSTICE	PROCEDURAL JUSTICE	DISTRIBUTIONAL JUSTICE
1. My stakes/rights in the environment are recognized.	5. I have the opportunity to meaningfully participate in environmental decision-making.	9. The impacts of environmental management decisions are fairly distributed.
2. The historic and cultural links between my community and the sea are recognised by broader society.	6. I know who to contact when clashes of interest occur in relation to decision-making processes.	10. Government distributes resources in a way that makes it possible to live well along the coast.
3. All economic sectors in our community are valued equally.	7. Conflicts between different users of the sea are solved fairly when they arise.	11. The benefits of Blue Growth/coastal economy are shared fairly across communities.
4. Minorities are a significant resource to the local community.	8. My identity does not prevent my participation in local decision-making.	12. Blue growth also benefits vulnerable groups (health/poverty/insecurity).
13. Life is better in the city-centres.		

For our study, the Academic leads and hosts in the six TCLs carefully selected a diverse sample of stakeholders from their networks—the P-set—including water owners, business owners, fishers, civil society representatives, self-employed individuals, school principals, local administration employees, immigrants, NGO representatives, and youth, all operating within a shared context.

Participants were selected to reflect different social groups, guided by the ‘Leaving No One Behind’ principle. Sample selection built on a EmpowerUs governance audit (Flannery et al. 2024 – Deliverable 2.1), which was itself a purposive set identified through stratified sampling to capture relevant actors and perspectives across each community. Within each group, participants were purposively selected based on interest and availability, emphasizing inclusivity.

Q-methodology assumes a limited number of coherent viewpoints shared by like-minded stakeholders (Barry and Proops 1999, Cotton 2015, Watts and Stenner 2012). Therefore, our sampling focused on individuals likely to hold differing viewpoints, aligned with the 13 statements in the Q-set, with 8 to 20 respondents per TCL to ensure diversity. In TCL Åland (Finland), two fisheries respondents preferred to complete a single survey together (FIN_2). In total, 63 respondents participated in the baseline survey, 35.9% of whom were female (Table 2). Although small by traditional survey standards, this aligns with Q methodology, which emphasises capturing the range of distinct viewpoints rather than statistical representativeness (Dieteren et al. 2023).

Table 2 Overview of participants in the Blue Q study.

Participants in the baseline survey

Identification number	TCL Burgas BULGARIA	TCL Eastern Limassol Region CYPRUS	TCL Åland FINLAND	TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands IRELAND	TCL Træna NORWAY	TCL Cap de Creus SPAIN
1	Higher education F	Scientist M	Small-scale coastal fisher M	Fisher M	Education M	NGO M
2	Industry M	Consultant M	Angler, water owner, resident M	Project manager F	Healthcare F	Scuba diver M
3	NGO M	Community council F	Small-scale coastal fishers M/F	Manager M	Self-employed M	Recreational fisher M
4	Citizen, business owner M	Community council M	Tourism sector, angling M	Scientist M	Fisher M	Recreational fisher M
5	NGO M	Coastal resident, immigrant F	Angler, resident, youth M	Manager M	Self-employed M	Fisher M
6	Resident, business owner F	Business owner M	Coastal resident, water owner F	Manager M	Business owner F	Civil society F
7	Municipality F	Citizen M	Small-scale coastal fisher M	Business owner M	Business owner M	Civil society M
8	Municipality F	Education F		Business owner M	Municipality F	Civil society F
9	Resident F	Education, former business owner M			Business M	Recreational fisher M
10					Worker M	Fisher M
11						Civil society M
12						Scuba diver M
13						Fisher M
14						Civil society F
15						NGO F
16						Fisher M
17						Fisher M
18						Scuba diver M
19						Fisher M
20						Manager F

3.1.2 Q sorting exercises

The Q-sorting data collection exercise was implemented in 2023 in collaboration between Nordland Research Institute (NRI) and the academic leads and hosts of the TCLs, who received training and guidance materials from NRI. A standard distribution grid was used for both in-person sessions, with flash cards overlaid on a poster of the sorting pyramid, and online sessions facilitated via Miro on Microsoft Teams. Respondents followed the recommended Q-method protocol (Molenveld 2020, van Exel and de Graaf 2005), categorizing 13 Blue Q-set statements in random order according to agreement, disagreement, or neutrality, and assigning scores from -3 (least agree) to +3 (most agree) in a forced normal distribution (see Table 3). Participants articulated their reasoning aloud during the sorting process, refining their choices until satisfied. They were explicitly asked to reflect on their reasons for each choice, as this is a key part of the Q-sort process and critical for subsequent analysis. Interviewers recorded these reflections and later prepared them for collaborative analysis with NRI.

3.1.3 Q-analyses: quantitative and qualitative

The Q sorts for each TCL have been analysed separately using Principal Component Analysis with Varimax (orthogonal) rotation using the open source PQMethod software (Schmolck 2014). Following a classic determination, the Factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.00 were considered (Brown 1993, Watts and Stenner 2012, Rahma et al. 2020), and subsequently automatic flagging in PQMethod was utilised to induce model Q-sorts (Watts and Stenner 2012).

The resultant Factor arrays underwent qualitative interpretation using the "crib sheet" method (Watts and Stenner 2012). This interpretive phase involved collaborative analysis with the academic leads from each TCL. The findings were deliberated upon, leading to the development of a collective interpretation, which was subsequently reviewed by the TCLs. The academic leads translated participants' reasons for choice from the local languages into English for analysis with NRI, ensuring that all reflections could be systematically incorporated into the collaborative interpretation. These interpretations were informed by both the statistical analysis results and the contextual knowledge possessed by the TCL academic leads. Factor descriptions primarily relied on distinctive statements identified for each Factor, where one Factor exhibited significantly different viewpoints compared to others. For each TCL, the Blue Q-method results yielded between one and three Factors, representing distinct groups of viewpoints. Interpretations were developed by examining statements where Factors disagreed versus agreed, highlighting the main patterns and perspectives of participants while omitting repetitions or secondary details. The results of this baseline survey are presented per TCL in Chapter 4.1.1 and compared across all TCLs in Chapter 4.1.2.

3.2 Evaluation survey – Likert-scale and qualitative interviews

Building on the results of the baseline survey, we developed an evaluation questionnaire to explore perceived changes over time in Blue Justice and empowerment among participants in EmpowerUs. The questionnaire consisted of two components: (1) Likert-scale questions to measure agreement or frequency, and (2) corresponding open-ended follow-up questions to capture qualitative insights. The survey specifically targeted participants who had actively engaged in one or more EmpowerUs activities, including workshops, pilot implementations, and ocean literacy events. The questionnaire (see Annex 7.1) included 15 questions: the first and last were open-ended only, while the remaining 13 combined a Likert-scale item with a related qualitative follow-up. Question 1 asked about the respondent's involvement in the project; Questions 2–4 addressed general perceptions of changes in empowerment; Questions 5, 6, 7, 10, and 11 explored Blue Justice dimensions, based on five overarching topics from the Q study results; Questions 8–9 examined nature connectedness; and Questions 12–14 assessed the TEPs. Question 15 invited respondents to add any further comments. The questionnaire was translated into Bulgarian, Greek (Cyprus), Finnish/Swedish, Norwegian, and Catalan/Spanish by the host organisations. Surveys were administered both in person and online. All qualitative responses were recorded, with TCL hosts providing anonymised English-language summaries in KoboToolbox.

A total of 49 participants completed the survey: Burgas (8), Eastern Limassol Region (6), Åland (7), Connemara and the Aran Islands (8), Træna (10), and Cap de Creus (9) (see Table 3).

Table 3 Overview of participants in the evaluation survey.

Participants in the evaluation survey

Identification number	TCL Burgas BULGARIA	TCL Eastern Limassol Region CYPRUS	TCL Åland FINLAND	TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands IRELAND	TCL Træna NORWAY	TCL Cap de Creus SPAIN
1	NGO	Community council	Government	Manager	Worker in local business	Scientist
2	Private sector	Community council	Business owner	Manager	Municipality	Business owner
3	Education	Project manager	Manager	Manager	Municipality	Business owner
4	Municipality	Director	Manager	Manager	Municipality	Business owner
5	NGO, community activism	Citizen	Fisher	Manager	Municipality	Regional director in public sector
6	Education	Citizen	Scientist	Project officer	Business owner	Civil society
7	NGO, higher education		Manager	Chairperson	Municipality	Civil society
8				Chairperson	Business owner	Scientist
9				Manager	Self-employed	Scientist
10					Municipality	

Quantitative data from the Likert-scale responses were analysed separately for each TCL by gathering results in Excel to prepare figures illustrating both average score and distribution of answers for each question (results in Chapter 4.2.1). Qualitative responses were analysed line-by-line for each participant in NVivo using inductive coding, with some deductive codes developed during analysis (see Annex 7.2). For each country, a thematic summary was developed covering: (1) Blue Justice dimensions, (2) overall changes in empowerment perceptions, (3) Avelino's power dimensions, (4) multi-level perspectives, and (5) perceived successes and failures in empowerment. These thematic summaries are presented individually for each TCL in Section 4.2.1 and then collectively analysed in Section 4.2.2 to highlight similarities and differences across all six TCLs.

3.3 Methodological reflections: strengths, scope and limitations

In this section, we reflect on the scope and limitations of the two main methodological approaches applied in this deliverable: the baseline study and the evaluation survey. The aim is not to undermine the validity of the methods, but to acknowledge their contextual boundaries and to demonstrate awareness of how these influence the interpretation of results.

Baseline survey

The baseline study has some contextual limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Firstly, there is a limitation in representation as most participants were drawn from the networks of the host organizations, potentially resulting in homogeneity within participant groups.

This risk was intentionally mitigated through the stratified design of the purposeful sample, which sought to include a range of perspectives.

Additionally, the translation of statements into the local language of the TCLs may have resulted in different interpretations. Some participants found it difficult to understand concepts such as “Blue Growth”. Furthermore, some participants felt compelled to categorise statements as “agree” even when they disagreed, due to the design of the Q study (forced distribution). Blue-Q statements have been developed for all TCLs, although their relative relevance varied by context. Not all labs did transcriptions and not all informants reflected out loud. These variations are important to acknowledge, as they shape the depth and comparability of the data. We are also aware that using 13 statements in the Q-Set is relatively low compared to many Q-methodology studies. A recent systematic review found an average of around 41 statements (range: 8-117), with most studies employing 30-50 statements to capture sufficient nuance of viewpoints (Dieteren et al. 2023). We chose a smaller set to avoid over-burdening participants who were already volunteering their time and effort, while still ensuring coverage of the core dimensions of Blue Justice and empowerment.

A more detailed and nuanced reflection on the application and methodological challenges of Q methodology is provided in the chapter “Q methodology – exploring local views of empowerment” (Spiering and Bratt 2025) in the Deliverable 5.2 *Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies* (Gustavsson et al. 2025).

Comparability between TCLs

When interpreting similarities and differences across TCLs, it is essential to consider structural and contextual factors, such as variations in governance (decentralised vs. centralised) and local socio-political contexts, which may influence procedural empowerment and other perceptions beyond the effects of EmpowerUs interventions. Finland and Åland enjoy decentralised structures that facilitate local decision-making, while Cyprus and Bulgaria operate in more centralised systems where local influence is limited. These institutional contexts partly explain why some communities reported higher procedural empowerment than others. By explicitly situating EmpowerUs findings in their broader political, social, and economic environments, we avoid over-attributing observed differences solely to project activities.

Evaluation survey

While the initial target in the evaluation survey was 10–15 respondents per TCL, some hosts reported stakeholder fatigue and limited follow-up to avoid overburdening participants. Moreover, recruiting participants was challenging as the project/pilot activities were still ongoing, so many people in the TCLs did not see the relevance of discussing the effects of the project at such an early stage. Since respondents were mostly those who had been engaged with EmpowerUs over a longer period, social desirability bias should be considered when interpreting their responses. Importantly, the evaluation survey was directly informed by the Blue Q baseline survey, enabling us to trace how perceptions of empowerment and justice evolved over time and across project activities.

In line with the EmpowerUs Gender, Equality, and Diversity (GED) Plan (Gustavsson and Midthaug Solnør 2024 – Deliverable 1.1), the methodological design of this deliverable has aimed to recognise and address the intersectional diversity of coastal communities. The inclusion of gender, age, ethnicity, and socio-economic background was encouraged in all stages of data collection and analysis, ensuring the research reflects the experiences and needs of groups often marginalised in marine and coastal governance. While not all TCLs were equally successful in capturing these complexities, targeted interviews and participatory methods helped to surface the lived experiences of diverse ‘users of the sea’, adding important nuance to the evaluation.

4 Results

This section presents the results of two surveys 1) the baseline survey conducted in 2023, and 2) the evaluation survey conducted in spring 2025. Together, these surveys allow us to explore how coastal communities perceive their own empowerment in relation to Blue Justice and the blue economy, and how these perceptions may have evolved through their engagement in EmpowerUs.

The baseline survey results, analysed using the Blue Q-methodology, are outlined for each of the distinct Factors identified in each of the six TCLs. Each Factor is introduced with a descriptive label and a concise explanation summarising its core perspective. To illustrate the analytical process, a full interpretation is provided only for the first Factor in TCL Burgas (Bulgaria). For all other Factors, summary interpretations are presented to improve readability. Full interpretations can be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request. The Factor descriptions draw on both the evaluation of the Blue Q-statements and qualitative insights from interviews. In Section 4.1.2, a comparative analysis of the baseline results for all TCLs is provided. The comparability across six diverse contexts was enabled by the Blue Q design, which offered shared dimensions of empowerment and justice while allowing for place-specific interpretation.

The evaluation survey results are then presented for each TCL individually in Chapter 4.2.1, combining quantitative and qualitative analyses. Finally, in Chapter 4.2.2, shared and distinctive aspects across TCLs are synthesised.

4.1 Baseline survey 2023/2024

4.1.1 Baseline survey results per TCL

Baseline results in TCL Burgas (Bulgaria)

Factor rotation TCL Burgas

Applying the criterion of only including Factors with a significant loading of at least two respondents after rotation, TCL Burgas yielded two Factors. These two Factors account for 64% of the total variance, surpassing the recommended threshold of 35% to 40%. The Factors demonstrate high to very high reliability, with an average reliability coefficient of 0.8. Both Factors have a composite reliability exceeding 0.8 (Factor 1: 0.952, Factor 2: 0.889), and the standard error of the Factor z-scores is 0.218 for Factor 1 and 0.333 for Factor 2. Five respondents significantly loaded onto Factor 1, while two respondents significantly loaded onto Factor 2 (Table 4). Notably, Factor 2 is a bipolar Factor, with both positive and negative significant loadings, indicating opposing viewpoints among the two respondents (Watts and Stenner, 2012). After conducting a qualitative analysis of Factor 2, we have decided not to include it in the study. This is because the opposing viewpoints do not result in a meaningful description of the context. As such, we concentrate on Factor 1, which accounts for 41% of the exploratory variables, exceeding the recommended threshold of 35 to 40%. When attempting to increase the number of Factors, the additional Factors only had one significant loading each and greater standard error of z-scores.

Later, the qualitative analysis shows that BUL1, BUL4, and BUL6 share viewpoints of Factor 1 and the explanation of that Factor also applies, whereas BUL2 differs somewhat. BUL4 exhibited weak and negative loadings on Factors 1 and 2 respectively, and BUL6 exhibited similar positive loadings on both Factors (Table 4). The background of these four participants will be considered later.

Table 4 Loadings of two Factors TCL Burgas.

		Loadings	
QSORT		1	2
1	BUL1	0.1687	0.8482X
2	BUL2	0.1677	-0.8648X
3	BUL3	0.9018X	0.0103
4	BUL4	0.0070	-0.2220
5	BUL5	0.7677X	0.4178
6	BUL6	0.3969	0.4539
7	BUL7	0.8562X	0.1720
8	BUL8	0.7961X	-0.3469
9	BUL9	0.8532X	-0.0361
% expl.Var.		41	23

Dominant perspectives in TCL Burgas

Full interpretation: Perspective 1 in TCL

Burgas - "Environmental concerns and mistrust of fairness in Blue Growth and decision processes"

Core themes: a focus on environmental issues, scepticism about fairness in Blue Growth benefits and decision-making, and a sense of disempowerment despite procedural access.

The five respondents with Q sorts loading onto Factor 1 consist of voluntary sector and municipal workers (three women and two men): two NGO experts, one participant working as head of department in Burgas municipality, a representative in the municipal council of Burgas who is also a local activist, and a locally active citizen and volunteer.

Table 5 Item ranking TCL Burgas Factor 1.

Respondents of Factor 1 are generally concerned with environmental issues and are positive towards sustainable solutions. The focus in that group is on fairness aspects indicated by three statements about fairness on minus 3 and minus 2. It is strongly disagreed that the benefits of Blue Growth have been shared equally across communities (st11 at minus 3), that conflicts between different users of the sea would be resolved fairly (st7 at minus 2), and that the impacts of environmental management decisions would be distributed fairly (st9 at minus 2). In their reflections, respondents related statement 11 to the concentration of profit among a select few individuals rather than being distributed across the community. Some associated this perceived unfairness with corruption in Bulgaria, citing for example the weak implementation of laws or the existence of corruption schemes associated with speculating with or not reporting the value added tax properly. These perceptions speak to a tendency to distrust governmental institutions. It is worth noting that corruption is often used as a narrative for diagnosing social problems and not merely as a concrete, readily identifiable aspect (Pardo 2004, Doshi and Ranganathan 2019, Antonova 2024).

On another note, participants in Factor 1 stress the community's dependence on dominant economic patterns, especially tourism, as a fairness concern. Not everyone benefits from the industry's profit. One participant noted that seasonal tourism used to be the norm, but with increased development, it no longer generates profits for many. Generating profits is particularly difficult for small business owners, while others have profited greatly from speculative investments. Another aspect that was mentioned relates to profits from selling land during periods of land speculation. A participant outlined that this can indirectly lead to drug abuse, as people earn large sums of money quickly and are unable to invest it sustainably. Instead, they sell their property and are left with a large amount of money that they do not know how to manage. These stories create the impression that while there may be great developments along the coastline, they have not benefited communities overall.

One participant mentioned the unanticipated consequences of industrial expansion north of Burgas, specifically regarding unintended and unfair side effects.

The Factor 1 group also focuses on procedural issues. Statements 8 and 6, both ranked at plus 2 indicate that the respondents are familiar with decision-making processes and how to participate, having experience with the system through their occupations (Table 5). However, at the opposite end, the statements concerned with the fairness of conflict solving and environmental management decisions (st. 7 and 9), and how different economic sectors are valued (st. 3), are rated at minus 2 and minus 1 respectively. In this sense, respondents expressed that even if they give their opinion, they feel that it does not matter.

With statements 12 and 11 ranked at the two extremes (plus and minus 3), this group holds strong opinions regarding Blue Growth and economic activity (Table 5). They believe that the economic development of the coastline benefits vulnerable people through employment. However, they also feel that the benefits are not distributed fairly, as outlined above. Furthermore, it appears that statement 12 was interpreted in an aspirational manner, rather than reflecting the current situation. In TCL Burgas, the term "vulnerable" refers to socially disadvantaged groups, such as the elderly, mothers, and children. Participants expect indirect benefits of Blue Growth on these groups. If taxes are raised, this could potentially provide more social benefits, such as pensions or child support.

The Blue Q-analysis shows that in the context of TCL Burgas, the terms "minority" and "vulnerable groups" evoke quite different interpretations. When discussing minorities, respondents typically associate this with Roma people. They feel that the community in general does not perceive them as a significant resource (st. 4 at minus 1). One respondent referred to minorities as refugees, citing Burgas' history as a city of refugees dating back to the Balkan wars. Currently, minorities in the area include Russians and Ukrainians, but they are often viewed as disintegrated and undervalued by the community (st. 4 at minus 1).

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Burgas "Environmental concerns and mistrust of fairness in Blue Growth and decision processes"

Factor 1 respondents are generally environmentally conscious and supportive of sustainable solutions, but express strong concerns about fairness in Blue Growth. They reject the idea that benefits are equally shared across communities, that conflicts between sea users are resolved fairly, or that environmental management impacts are distributed equitably. Some link this perceived unfairness to corruption in Bulgaria, where weak law enforcement and tax manipulation are seen as systemic problems. Participants also highlight economic dependence on tourism, noting that its profits are unevenly distributed. Small businesses often struggle while others gain from speculative investments, especially in land sales, sometimes leading to harmful social consequences like drug abuse. Despite coastal development, they feel the community has not benefited as a whole. While some are familiar with decision-making processes through their work, they often believe their input has little effect. The

group recognises potential benefits of Blue Growth for vulnerable groups—interpreted locally as the elderly, mothers, and children—especially through improved tax-based social support, but views this as more aspirational than current reality. In discussing minorities, most associate the term with Roma, who are seen as undervalued, while refugees and other groups (e.g., Russians, Ukrainians) are viewed as poorly integrated into the community.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

Factor 1 reflects procedural empowerment in that respondents feel knowledgeable about, and able to access, decision-making processes. This access is perceived as independent of personal identity (neutral recognitional dimension). However, participants doubt that their input leads to fair or equitable outcomes, signalling strong disempowerment in the distributional dimension — particularly regarding the benefits of Blue Growth and the fairness of environmental management decisions.

Participants not loading on Factor 1

Respondents who did not load on Factor 1 were BUL1, BUL2, BUL4 and BUL6. BUL1 is a scientist, BUL2 is a technician, BUL4 is a local citizen and BUL6 is a business owner. BUL1 and BUL2 loaded on a second Factor with opposing viewpoints, but this was not included in the analysis as described above.

Table 6 Participants in TCL Burgas not loading on Factor 1.

The qualitative analysis showed that, although all four respondents did not load significantly on Factor 1, they align with it thematically. While their ratings on individual statements differ (e.g., Factor 1 rates statements 9 and 11 at -2, whereas BUL1 rates statements 3 and 10 at -2), the overall thematic pattern is consistent. From a narrative perspective, statements 3, 9, 10, and 11 collectively convey a similar message about the importance of fair distribution. Factor 1 and the other four respondents would agree that there is a lack of equitable distribution of resources across sectors and regions, and a lack of sharing of the impacts and benefits of environmental management and economic development. BUL4 strongly emphasises the inequitable distribution of environmental management decisions. BUL6 interprets st. 9 (on plus 1) about the fairness of resource distribution in the benefit of nature, in the sense that there are protected areas. But then the same respondent reverses this by giving the example of a park in the southern part of the coastline near to the Turkish border where natural resources have been under threat from construction and development.

BUL2 discusses conflicts or unfairness in governance, specifically referring to Atanasovsko Lake (st. 7 at minus 3). According to this respondent, it is unfair that large developments and constructions such as motorways are allowed to be built, even though “everyone says they want to preserve nature, but in the end, they focus on profit”. The consequences are harmful run-off into the lake and costly expenses for salt producers who have to pump it out. The lack of preventive measures and funding from the government to restore and reduce the negative impact on nature is perceived as unfair (st. 1 at minus 2). BUL2 does not speak about corruption in general, but also emphasises aspects of fairness; in this case very specifically with what is happening with the lake and phrasing it as a governance issue, what is prioritised and what is left out or not considered. The participant highlights

that the percentage of money spent on the lake is not at all in proportion to what is spent on developments around the lake, and this again relates to perceptions of disempowerment.

BUL1 would be the most qualitatively different from the other respondents. As a natural scientist, this respondent was in a strong analytical mode and did not want to comment on the ordering of the statements without having scientific information about them. However, like the others, this participant placed the fairness-related statements low (st. 10 and st. 3 at minus 2), indicating a perception that resources are not allocated fairly and that different economic sectors are not equally valued in their community. At the same time, the participant emphasised the importance of equity and sustainability across sectors and regions.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Burgas

Most respondents in TCL Burgas either agree or are neutral about having the opportunity to participate in environmental decision-making. As mentioned above, this does not mean that they believe that their voice is heard and that the results are fair. The two business owners (BUL4 and BUL6) express concerns about unfairness, including a lack of distribution of benefits from economic development and unfair conflict resolution between stakeholders with different interests. They do not rate statements about fairness as negatively as Factor 1, but rate conflict resolution at minus 1 and government distribution at minus 2. Several respondents directly or indirectly mention corruption in relation to government decisions, one of the respondents mentions that "it's a wild business..." in the natural parks. In contrast, statement 10 about government distribution of resources scores plus 1 on Factor 1. This may indicate that BULG4 and BULG6 have less trust in the government than the Factor 1 group.

The aspects that distinguish Factor 1 from the other Q-sorts are the sorting of statements 12, 13, 1, 7 (Table 5). Both business owners and BULG2, who works in the private sector, feel that the cultural and historical links with the sea are recognised by the wider society. This is not the case for Factor 1 and BULG1. This may be because their businesses focus on local, traditional food, because they are interested in local history and/or because they are active members of the community and are therefore recognised.

Baseline results in TCL Eastern Limassol Region (Cyprus)

Factor rotation TCL Eastern Limassol Region

We identified two predominant perspectives on empowerment discourse within TCL Eastern Limassol Region. Together, these perspectives explained 58% of the total variance, surpassing the recommended threshold of 35% to 40% (Watts and Stenner 2012). It is noteworthy that all nine respondents showed significant loadings on one of these perspectives. The Factors demonstrated high reliability, with an average reliability coefficient of 0.68.

Table 7 Loadings of two Factors TCL Eastern Limassol Region.

QSORT	1	2
1 CYP1	0.6643X	-0.3264
2 CYP2	-0.1221	0.6888X
3 CYP3	0.6025X	0.5282
4 CYP4	0.0985	0.8468X
5 CYP5	0.5817X	-0.2250
6 CYP6	0.6873X	0.1357
7 CYP7	0.7313X	0.5353
8 CYP8	0.7413X	0.4580
9 CYP9	0.0726	0.6023X
% expl.Var.	30	28

Dominant perspectives in TCL Eastern Limassol Region

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Eastern Limassol Region "Rural stakeholders concerned about unfair government decisions and lack of environmental influence"

Core themes: place-based connection, dissatisfaction with government decisions, perceived unfairness in environmental management, and limited influence despite accessibility to local decision-making.

This perspective is defined by six participants: CYP1 is a female technician at a research institute, CYP3 works for one of the three different community councils in the TCL area, CYP5 is a female non-Cypriot living in the coastal area of the TCL, CYP6 is a local business owner, CYP7 is a citizen living on the coastal side of the TCL, and CYP8 is an active member of a local parent’s association. Explaining 30% of total variance, this was the strongest discourse in TCL Eastern Limassol Region.

Table 8 Item ranking TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 1.

This perspective is rooted in a strong place-based attachment to rural living, even though these communities are close to urban centres. Respondents express procedural empowerment through their ability to access and participate in local decision-making, with local authorities perceived as approachable. Recognitionally empowerment is neutral, as personal identity is not seen as a barrier to participation. However, there is marked disempowerment in the distributional dimension, particularly regarding the siting of industrial projects — such as a waste management facility, the main energy centre of the island, and a planned industrial aquaculture harbour — within or adjacent to their community. These are perceived to diminish local attractiveness, especially for tourism, reflecting low trust in government. Although Blue Growth is seen as potentially beneficial for job creation, its concrete meaning and local benefits remain uncertain, and respondents feel their voices are ultimately not heard.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

Stakeholders in Factor 1 feel procedurally empowered in that local decision-making structures are accessible, and they can voice their opinions without identity-based barriers. However, this access rarely leads to actual influence, as decision-making processes are perceived as unresponsive. The lack of collective reactions, which could support a better response from governments are uncommon. Distributionally, respondents feel disempowered due to the concentration of industrial developments in their area, which they believe are unfairly sited and poorly managed, with negative consequences for tourism and quality of life. While Blue Growth is viewed as having potential to create jobs, its benefits remain uncertain and unevenly distributed. Recognitionally, participants do not feel their environmental concerns are sufficiently acknowledged by authorities, contributing to a broader sense of exclusion and low trust in government.

Summary interpretation: Factor 2 TCL Eastern Limassol Region "Close to power but disempowered in environmental decisions: Advocating Blue Growth while critiquing government inconsistencies"

Core themes: the Factor reflects the group's close ties to local decision-making, frustration with their lack of influence in environmental matters, and emphasis on balancing industrial development with environmental protection.

This perspective is defined by three participants: CYP2 is a company owner who also voluntarily offer support to one of the community councils, CYP4 works for one of the community councils and CYP9 is

a schoolteacher and former business owner. Explaining 28% of total variance, this was the second strongest discourse in TCL Eastern Limassol Region.

Table 9 Item ranking TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 2.

Given the extreme rankings of the statements for this group, their main focus is on perceived disempowerment, particularly in environmental decision-making. All participants are white males with close ties to the local council and proximity to decision-making power, giving them easier access to processes and the ability to voice opinions. In Cyprus, however, where everyone knows “who to talk to,” such access does not guarantee influence. The group believes that future Blue Growth could and should benefit vulnerable groups, reflecting a broader pro-development stance that assumes benefits will trickle down, even if indirectly, to those most in need. Despite this, they strongly disagree that they have the power to participate in environmental decision-making or that their stake in the environment is recognised. While their interest leans toward economic development rather than environmental protection, they do value the environment and criticise what they see as incoherent governmental strategies. The promotion of a marine protected area (MPA) adjacent to an area where an industrial development is being planned creates further mistrust about what the MPA will actually protect. To them, this environmental protection appears tokenistic, a gesture without an integrated vision, and one likely to backfire. They see local participation as a box-ticking exercise, ultimately overshadowed by the economic power of industry. They also disagree that the benefits of the Blue Economy are fairly shared across communities and note that resource distribution does not support a good standard of living on the coast. Unlike many other TCL Factors, this group agrees that life is better in the city, citing access to services such as hospitals and schools — though this is not central to their perspective.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

The essence of this Factor lies in a nuanced interplay of empowerment and disempowerment among participants, primarily focusing on areas where they perceive a lack of agency. While individuals within this group, all white males with proximity to local council and decision-making power, enjoy easier access and influence in processes, they feel sidelined in environmental decision-making. They advocate for Blue Growth initiatives to benefit vulnerable groups, recognizing their own role in promoting industrial development. Despite valuing the environment, they critique governmental inconsistencies and tokenistic environmental protection efforts, emphasizing the need for a coherent strategy. This Factor underscores disparities in resource distribution, with economic interests often overshadowing environmental concerns. Local participation is viewed sceptically as a token gesture, with economic interests ultimately dictating outcomes. Overall, it seems to the group that the people in the local governments would need to have more power/influence in the decision-making processes. The narratives coming out from this group, reflect the conflicting narratives communities are facing, in which environmental protection (MPA) lies opposite, or against community development or blue economy.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Eastern Limassol Region

Both groups agree that they know who to contact if needed as Cyprus has a small size and partocratic structures, whilst clientelist relationships are present. Additionally, both groups share the perception that the government does not distribute resources in a way that enables a good standard of living along the coast and that their opinions are not considered (not all coastal areas are equal). Participants in Factor 2 are individuals who are closer to local decision-making bodies. However, they disagree that they have the opportunity to participate meaningfully in environmental decision-making, as the final decisions on the issues which intersect issues linked to the blue economy, marine protection and coastal development are made at a higher governance level. It is also important to note that though there seems to be an agreement with the statement that suggests that “Blue Growth also benefits vulnerable groups”, the two groups also feel that resources are not fairly distributed. This also shows how society understands the concept of growth (as specific type of infrastructure over others, as well as over protection). The two groups hold opposing views on the statement that “life is better in the city-centres.” Group 1 strongly disagrees with this statement, while Group 2 agrees with it.

Baseline results in TCL Åland (Finland)

Factor rotation TCL Åland

We included only Factors with at least two significantly loading respondents after the varimax rotation. This resulted in two Factors with 4 respondents significantly loading on Factor 1, and 2 respondents significantly loading on Factor 2 (Table 10). One respondent (FIN7) lacked a significant loading on one of these. This was a multigenerational fisher whose sorts and reflections had similarities to both Factors. The two Factors together explain 76% of the total variance, exceeding the recommended threshold of 35-40%. Both Factors had an average reliability coefficient of 0.8, the composite reliability was 0.941 for Factor 1 and 0.889 for Factor 2. The standard error of Factor Z-scores was 0.243 and 0.333 for Factor 1 and Factor 2 respectively.

Table 10 Loadings of two Factors TCL Åland.

QSORT	Loadings	
	1	2
1 FIN1	0.8815X	0.3223
2 FIN2	0.5940X	0.5391
3 FIN3	0.4115	0.7117X
4 FIN4	0.9636X	-0.0260
5 FIN5	0.0234	0.9400X
6 FIN6	0.8606X	0.4047
7 FIN7	0.5077	0.4283
% expl. Var.	46	30

Dominant perspectives in TCL Åland

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Åland “Satisfaction with local involvement but frustration with fairness and influence in decision-making at a higher level”

Core themes: the Factor captures the group's contentment with local decision-making access, alongside concerns about fairness and their limited influence at national or EU levels, especially regarding environmental policies affecting fishers.

Three men and one woman associate with the perspective of Factor 1: a part time fisher, a water owner and recreational angler, a fishing guide, and a banker. All participants are local to the TCL area. The communities where these participants live, are not experiencing much pressure from Blue Growth, so some participants found statements about Blue Growth less relevant. Some participants had difficulties with the academic language of the statements, and some thought they were too general. Others thought it was a fun and useful exercise. This Factor perspective explains 46 % of the total variance and also accounts for the majority of the respondents of the Åland study (4 out of 7).

Table 11 Item ranking TCL Åland Factor 1.

This Factor indicates a general satisfaction with living in the TCL area and a familiarity with decision-making processes and the ability to partake in them. Participants enjoy living in the TCL area and feel that they have equal rights to the ocean and its resources, but also perceive the situation as “equally bad.” In their experience, there are good opportunities for influencing decision-making processes, especially locally, and it is not difficult to find out who to contact regarding conflicts or decisions in Åland. However, making an impact or influencing larger governmental decisions at the national or EU level feels difficult and unfair to the participants.

This is especially linked to seal and cormorant protection policies, which are perceived as negatively impacting fish resources and fishers. Other concerns include eutrophication and potential impacts of offshore wind developments on fish stocks. Participants feel more neutral about Blue Growth and economic aspects, which may be related to the academic and intangible language used in discussions, as well as limited Blue Growth pressures within their communities.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

The participants whose Q sorts load on Factor 1 generally have a strong sense of place and feel they have equal rights to the sea’s resources, although conflict resolution and participatory processes are seen as imperfect, especially beyond the local level. Regarding Blue Justice, they strongly emphasise procedural justice, valuing opportunities to participate in decision-making processes. However, they feel less empowered in terms of distributional and recognitional justice, particularly concerning fairness and their ability to influence decisions at higher governance levels (Finland and the EU). Participants also express perceptions of disempowerment related to the distribution of resources and the impacts of environmental policies. Some members of this group possess detailed knowledge and awareness of Åland’s decision-making processes due to their experience, position, or active involvement.

Summary interpretation: Factor 2 TCL Åland “Deep local ties, but frustration at being left out of higher-level decisions on fisheries and the environment”

Core themes: strong ties to their rural community and cultural practices, as well as concerns about limited influence over key decisions on fishing rights, offshore wind and EU policies that affect their livelihoods.

Three participants associate with this perspective: one couple (who did the Q sort together), both lifelong fishers and water owners, and above 60 years old; and a male recreational angler below 18 years old. All are local coastal residents from the TCL area, and the couple live in an area with more resistance towards offshore wind. The participants in this group had difficulties understanding some of the statements, due to academic language, and thus required some explanations and examples. This perspective accounts for 30% of the total variance.

Table 12 Item ranking TCL Åland Factor 2.

This group demonstrates a strong connection to the area and prefers living in the rural setting over the city. They feel they have equal access to water and perceive that traditional and cultural fish products are recognised and valued within the local community. At the same time, they express dissatisfaction with how decisions are made and their ability to meaningfully participate in those processes. Key concerns relate to changes that make it difficult to pursue fishing as a main occupation on the Åland Islands. These include challenges in obtaining fishing rights, declining fish stocks, low fish prices, and the need to add value to products and sell directly to customers to make a living. At the local and national levels, some participants feel overruled in decisions regarding fishing rights in their co-managed waters and express distrust towards decision-making on offshore wind development in Åland. They feel their voices are largely ignored and that energy companies are prioritised over traditional livelihoods. On the EU level, concerns focus on seal protection policies and management, which are seen as negatively affecting fish resources.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

At the essence, Factor 2 participants also focus on a strong connection to place and feel recognised by the community at the local level, but feel unable to influence higher level decisions that affect quality of life and traditional, cultural activities linked to the use of the sea. In terms of Blue Justice categories, participants feel more empowered about distributional and recognitional aspects, related to recognition and fairness of resource distribution. However, they agree less with fairness aspects regarding environmental policy impact and the value given to diverse economic sectors. They feel disempowered about procedural aspects related to meaningful participation and knowing who to contact regarding clashes of interest.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Åland

In general, all participants strongly believe that life is not better in the city centres. They share a strong attachment to place and generally feel that, regardless of identity, people have equal rights to resources and to voice their opinion at the local governance level. Differences among perspectives relate to procedural aspects; in Factor 1, respondents feel more empowered to make an influence in decision-making, while the Factor 2 group feels more marginalised. This could be due to respondents in Factor 1 having experience being involved in local politics or decision-making processes, while respondents in Factor 2 include a very young person, and a couple that finds bureaucracy time consuming, and does not have as much experience with decision-making processes. The Factor groups are also distinguished by opposite perceptions of how government distributes resources. Respondents did not reflect out loud about this statement, but it may have been interpreted at different layers of governance. While Factor 1 may have related it to seal problems and national fish management, thus rated it negatively, Factor 2 may have interpreted it in terms of local subsidies for infrastructure, making it possible to live a good life in the coastal area.

Baseline results in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland)

Factor rotation in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Table 13 Loadings of two Factors TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands.

We established a criterion to include only Factors showing significant loadings from a minimum of two respondents after rotation (Brown 1980). In Table 13, we present these Factors alongside their respective loadings per respondent, indicated by a cross (X). Subsequently, we identified two predominant perspectives on empowerment discourse within TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands. Together, these perspectives explained 69% of the total variance, surpassing the recommended threshold of 35% to 40%. It is noteworthy that six respondents showed significant loadings on one of these perspectives. Two respondents (IRL_6 and IRL_7) did not load on either Factor. IRL_6 is a manager of a community cooperative and did not seem to have a direct connection with marine and coastal issues, and IRL_7 is a business owner running a restaurant and pub in the area and also did not have a strong connection with coastal issues. The Factors demonstrated high to very high reliability, with an average reliability coefficient of 0.8.

QSORT	1	2
1 IRL_1	0.7734X	0.3693
2 IRL_2	-0.3510	0.8716X
3 IRL_3	0.5220	0.7056X
4 IRL_4	0.3756	0.7921X
5 IRL_5	0.7682X	0.4788
6 IRL_6	0.4297	0.5417
7 IRL_7	0.3465	0.0752
8 IRL_8	0.9512X	-0.1296

Dominant perspectives in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands "Active local campaigners express concerns about unfair conflict resolution and marginalisation in marine decision-making"

Core themes: dissatisfaction with decision-making processes, particularly in relation to conflicts between marine users, while acknowledging their commitment to local activism and their ability to access decision-makers. They are critical of Blue Growth models such as offshore wind and aquaculture and stress the need for a more inclusive and balanced approach to coastal development.

This perspective is defined by three participants: a semi-retired fisherman, a manager of a community cooperative and an owner of a sports fishing company. Two of them were locals who had grown up in the TCL area and worked in traditional sectors, so both felt they could participate in local decision-making. Explaining 37% of total variance, this was the dominant discourse in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands.

Table 14 Item ranking TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 1.

Factor 1 in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands represents a group primarily concerned with dissatisfaction about how decisions are made and how certain groups tend to win out over others.

Despite this, participants are actively involved in local campaigning and activism and feel that they can at least be recognised and included in decision-making processes. A key concern is the strong disagreement over the fair resolution of conflicts between various sea users, especially in relation to offshore wind farm developments and their potential conflict with the fishing industry. Participants express apprehension that the expansion of MPAs and offshore wind projects may restrict fishing activities and increase pressures on the area. Additional conflicts include unclear regulations around seaweed harvesting, which currently rely more on traditional agreements than official rules, alongside concerns about overharvesting and unsustainable practices. There is also a significant conflict between sport fishing for salmon and trout and finfish aquaculture, with strong opposition to the latter due to perceived unfair conflict resolution. Participants feel the fisheries sector is undervalued compared to other industries, and coastal and fishing communities are not adequately recognised. They perceive that Ireland does not fully identify itself as a maritime nation, with a predominant focus on land-based agriculture that creates a disconnect between the national image and local fishing-dependent areas. Importantly, participants would place most statements on the negative side if the method allowed it, including statements that were actually rated positively. Therefore, positive placements do not necessarily indicate endorsement but rather a relatively weaker disagreement compared to other statements. For example, while they would not fully agree that the government distributes resources in a way that enables a good quality of life on the coast, they do recognise that some resources are available to support coastal communities.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

In essence, the analysis of relevant quotes show that the proponents' priority are the conflicts between various sea users, such as those between wind energy and fisheries, and aquaculture and angling. Respondents have strong opinions on these disputes. They criticise the current "Blue Growth" economic model, particularly regarding offshore wind and aquaculture, while recognizing the need for local economic development. Respondents acknowledge the trade-off between economic growth and environmental preservation, emphasising the importance of a balanced approach. Despite reservations, respondents see potential in contributing to local economic initiatives. However, they advocate for a more balanced and inclusive Blue Growth strategy that prioritises community concerns. This overall picture is also reflected in the Blue Justice categories as participants seem to feel more empowered on distributional issues and less empowered on recognitional issues. When it comes to procedural aspects, they feel strongly disempowered about fair conflict resolution and their inability to participate meaningfully in environmental decision-making, but they feel strongly empowered regarding their ability to contact relevant actors when conflicts of interest arise. It is also worth mentioning that their position in the community does not prevent them from participating in local decision-making.

Summary interpretation: Factor 2 TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands: "Disempowered but committed: Participants advocate for Blue Growth amid concerns over unfair decision-making and project delays"

Core themes: deep sense of disempowerment in relation to fairness in decision-making, particularly in relation to the stalled Páirc na Mara project, a proposed marine innovation park in Connemara whose rejection left many feeling excluded from transparent and fair planning, while also highlighting their active participation in environmental processes and their support for Blue Growth initiatives to address employment needs. This Factor highlights concerns about inequities in sectoral recognition and the perceived unfair distribution of resources and benefits.

This perspective is defined by three participants: a project manager, a manager of a community cooperative and a scientist. Explaining 32% of total variance, this was the second strongest discourse in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands.

Table 15 Item ranking TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 2.

This Factor reveals a strong sense of disempowerment among participants concerning fairness, particularly linked to recent events around the Páirc na Mara development. Environmental opposition, especially related to the water treatment plan, has halted the project, and participants fear the entire initiative might be jeopardised due to perceived unfair decision outcomes. Decision-making dynamics occur across multiple levels: while Galway County Council rejected the initial planning, participants feel their interests are undervalued at regional and national levels as well. Ambiguities in the management and harvesting of seaweed resources within the same community further exacerbate perceptions of inequity and unfairness. Despite these concerns, participants strongly believe that their stakes and rights in the environment are recognised, likely due to their defined institutional roles and direct governmental connections. They also feel they have meaningful opportunities to participate in environmental decision-making processes. There is notable support for Blue Growth industries driven by urgent employment needs, especially for young people facing limited job prospects. Projects like Páirc na Mara, coastal tourism, and seaweed harvesting are seen as important avenues for local economic development. However, concerns remain about the fair distribution of benefits from Blue Growth. The stalling of Páirc na Mara, alongside ongoing development in other sectors such as wind energy and aquaculture, fuels uncertainty about the project’s future and its benefits for the community. Additionally, the diversity among communities in Connemara and the Aran Islands means that economic developments in one area may not be viewed as advantageous by others.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

The essence of this Factor lies in establishing a clearer link between individual perspectives, decision-making processes, and the benefits of Blue Growth. Participants perceive value in developments like Páirc na Mara, coastal tourism, and seaweed harvesting, recognizing their roles within broader institutions. They emphasise the importance of delineating the connection between Blue Growth initiatives and benefits to local communities. Unlike the preceding Factor, where individual views predominated, here, participants have clearly defined roles within their institutions, fostering a more institutional perspective on environmental decision-making. This is similarly reflected in the Blue Justice Dimensions: Participants feel empowered regarding procedural matters and believe their stakes in the environment are acknowledged. However, they feel disempowered regarding the equal valuation of all economic sectors. They recognise their stakes and historic links but perceive disparities in sectoral recognition. Additionally, they remain neutral concerning distributional issues. Overall, the interplay between empowerment and disempowerment is complex, particularly in relation to recognition and fairness in environmental and economic domains.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Both Factors agree that they value living in rural areas, they both do not feel strongly about Blue Growth benefiting vulnerable groups and both do not weight the significance of minorities as resources for the community highly. There is a strong disagreement in both Factors regarding the opportunities for participation in environmental decision-making. Institutional respondents (Factor 2)

perceive that they can participate, while individualised people (Factor 1) disagree. In contrast, individuals in Factor 1 are aware of whom to contact in the event of conflicts of interest, although this does not significantly affect decision-making. Conversely, those in Factor 2 hold differing opinions as they do not feel adequately represented at a higher level. Due to an ongoing conflict regarding Páirc na Mara, those in Factor 2 disagree that the impacts of environmental management decisions are fairly distributed, while those in Factor 1 tend to agree but do not rate this statement as very important.

Baseline results in TCL Træna (Norway)

Table 16 Loadings of two Factors TCL Træna.

QSORT	1	2
1 NORW1	0.1076	0.8009X
2 NOR2	0.1082	0.8215X
3 NORW3	0.3691	0.7976X
4 NORW4	0.6261X	0.5808
5 NORW5	0.7691X	0.3494
6 NORW6	0.5988X	0.5671
7 NORW7	0.8092X	0.2802
8 NORW8	0.8131X	-0.0362
9 NORW9	0.5782	0.7086X
10 NORW10	0.7197X	0.2824

Factor rotation TCL Træna

We set a criterion to incorporate only Factors exhibiting significant loadings from a minimum of two respondents following rotation (Brown 1980). In Table 16, we display the Factors alongside their respective loadings per respondent, denoted by a cross X. Subsequently, we discerned two prevailing perspectives on empowerment discourse within TCL Træna. These perspectives collectively accounted for 71% of the total variance, exceeding the recommended threshold of 35% to 40%. Notably, 10 respondents exhibited significant loadings onto one of these perspectives. The Factors showcased high to very high reliability, with an average reliability coefficient of 0.8.

Dominant perspectives in TCL Træna

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Træna "Embracing Silence: Participants prioritise sustainable living amid disempowerment over fairness in environmental decision-making"

Core themes: Participants emphasise quality of life, a strong sense of place, and their prioritisation of sustainable, slow growth in Træna. They feel their environmental interests are acknowledged and their rights to access and enjoy nature are secure. Yet, paradoxically, they experience a deep sense of injustice regarding how resources and benefits are distributed, particularly in relation to Blue Growth and environmental policy. This juxtaposition of empowerment through recognition and disempowerment in terms of fairness is the defining feature of this discourse.

Six participants are significantly associated with this Factor: a fisher (NORW 4), a self-employed person (NORW5), two business owners (NORW6 and NORW7), one from the municipality (NORW8), and an employee (NORW10). Explaining 37% of the total variance, this is the dominant discourse in TCL Træna.

This Factor reveals a strong orientation toward sustainable living and local wellbeing. Participants reject urban life, strongly valuing the tranquillity and cultural distinctiveness of Træna. They highlight equal rights to enjoy nature, underlining how the natural environment is central to their quality of life. At the same time, they express ambivalence about whether vulnerable or minority groups fully benefit from Blue Growth. While acknowledging that migrant workers are indispensable for local industries such as fish processing, they also point to limited social integration, language barriers, and a lack of suitable community offerings. Perceptions of fairness and justice emerge as the most disempowering

dimension. Participants voice scepticism about whether the values and benefits of Blue Growth or environmental policies are fairly distributed, both locally and nationally. They refer to disparities between municipalities such as Træna and Lurøy, as well as concerns that wealthier or more powerful actors dominate decision outcomes. Similarly, conflicts in the coastal zone are not perceived as being resolved equitably, with smaller communities feeling overshadowed by larger or better-resourced interests. Despite these concerns, participants report a clear sense of recognition and agency at the local scale. They know whom to contact in case of conflicts and do not feel hindered by their personal identity in participating in local processes. This sense of recognition, however, does not translate into a belief that their voices matter in broader political or distributional outcomes.

In sum, Factor 1 highlights the paradox of empowerment in recognition but disempowerment in justice. While participants embrace the quiet and sustainable lifestyle that Træna affords, they remain deeply concerned about inequities in how resources, opportunities, and environmental responsibilities are distributed across communities and sectors.

Table 17 Item ranking TCL Træna Factor 1.

Summary interpretation: Factor 2 TCL Træna “Undervalued resources, ownership fears and transport problems in peripheral regions: the overlooked importance of Arctic coastal communities”

Core themes: This Factor reflects the specific concerns of Arctic coastal communities, where participants feel procedurally empowered through close ties to local governance but experience significant disempowerment over fairness in the distribution of resources and benefits. They highlight undervalued contributions of coastal regions, fears of external ownership and exploitation of marine resources, and persistent transport challenges that exacerbate their peripheral status.

Four participants are significantly associated with this Factor: a school principal (NORW1), a healthcare worker (NORW2), a self-employed person (NORW3), and a business sector representative (NORW9). Explaining a substantial share of variance, this Factor represents the second strongest discourse in TCL Træna.

This Factor reveals a strong sense of recognition and proximity at the local scale. Participants stress that they know whom to contact in case of conflicts and value the short distance to local decision-makers. Everyone is perceived to have a voice in municipal affairs, in contrast to larger contexts where voices feel diluted. This sense of procedural empowerment is reinforced by their ability to participate freely in community processes, though some roles (e.g. school principal) may impose constraints of neutrality. At the same time, participants articulate deep frustrations with fairness and distributional justice. They perceive the benefits of Blue Growth and environmental policy as unfairly distributed, with wealthier regions or larger companies capturing most of the gains. Several point to high fish quota prices, foreign ownership, and “big capitalism” as barriers that marginalise small-scale actors and young entrants. Transport challenges are repeatedly highlighted as a core grievance, with participants

perceiving deprioritised compared to neighbouring municipalities. These concerns reinforce perceptions that Træna’s contributions are undervalued in national budgets, while urban areas reap disproportionate benefits.

Participants also reflect on ownership and identity in relation to nature. While they affirm their equal rights to access and enjoy the environment, they express unease about increasing tourism pressure, particularly on vulnerable landscapes. This raises concerns that outside actors capitalise on local natural assets, threatening both ecological integrity and community ownership. Minority groups are acknowledged as essential for sustaining local industries, yet ambivalence remains around their social integration and the risk of exploitation as cheap labour.

In sum, Factor 2 underscores the paradox of strong procedural empowerment locally but persistent disempowerment in terms of distributional fairness. While participants feel recognised and capable of engaging directly with local authorities, they remain deeply concerned about external ownership, inequitable transport and infrastructure provision, and the undervaluation of Arctic coastal communities’ contributions to national prosperity.

Table 18 Item ranking TCL Træna Factor 2.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Træna

Both Factors emphasise the high quality of life on Træna and a strong sense of recognition of their environmental stakes. Neither Factor sees Blue Growth as particularly benefiting vulnerable groups, and both highlight ambivalence about the role of minorities as resources for the community. The key difference lies in their framing of disempowerment: Factor 1 prioritises sustainable living and tranquillity but expresses frustration with unfairness in resource distribution more implicitly, whereas Factor 2 strongly emphasises distributional injustice, external ownership, and transport inequalities as core grievances. While both acknowledge procedural empowerment at the local level, Factor 2 participants stress close access to decision-makers more explicitly than those in Factor 1.

Baseline results in TCL Cap de Creus (Spain)

Factor rotation TCL Cap de Creus

After the varimax rotation in that we included only Factors with at least two significantly loading respondents, TCL Cap de Creus resulted in three Factors with eight respondents significantly loading on Factor 1, five respondents loading on Factor 2 (an additional one SPAIN14 negatively loading), and four respondents significantly loading on Factor 3 (Table 19). Two respondents (SPAIN10 and SPAIN16) lacked a significant loading on one of these. SPAIN10 was a fisher whose sorts and reflections had similarities to both Factors, whereas SPAIN16 was another fisher and had similarities with Factor 1 (0.5360 on Factor 1). The three Factors together explain 69% of the total variance, exceeding the recommended threshold of 35-40%.

Table 19 Loadings of three Factors TCL Cap de Creus.

1 SPAIN1	-0.1128	0.7171X	-0.2993
2 SPAIN2	0.3760	0.0139	0.7042X
3 SPAIN3	0.0513	0.7030X	0.2758
4 SPAIN4	0.7670X	-0.4002	0.2510
5 SPAIN5	0.7487X	0.1733	0.2779
6 SPAIN6	0.8503X	0.1217	0.3993
7 SPAIN7	0.8008X	0.0117	0.3381
8 SPAIN8	0.8152X	0.2344	-0.0778
9 SPAIN9	0.7670X	-0.4002	0.2510
10 SPAIN10	0.5796	0.0780	0.5785
11 SPAIN11	-0.1063	0.7955X	0.1107
12 SPAIN12	0.4044	0.7432X	0.1744
13 SPAIN13	-0.0065	0.2100	0.8256X
14 SPAIN14	0.3030	-0.6476X	0.0811
15 SPAIN15	0.7459X	-0.3427	-0.3128
16 SPAIN16	0.5360	0.1411	0.2706
17 SPAIN17	0.0593	-0.0564	0.7066X
18 SPAIN18	0.4242	0.7524X	0.1218
19 SPAIN19	0.5827X	0.5646	-0.0730
20 SPAIN20	0.5623	-0.0612	0.7015X
% expl.Var.	31	21	17

Dominant perspectives in TCL Cap de Creus

Summary interpretation: Factor 1 TCL Cap de Creus
"Balancing tradition and tourism: Coastal Communities in Cap de Creus seek fair participation amidst Blue Growth pressures"

Core themes: participants feel empowered in environmental decision-making processes, but are concerned about the unequal distribution of benefits from the expanding tourism industry. While they value recognition and participation through workshops and social movements, traditional livelihoods such as fishing feel threatened by the unchecked growth of tourism and maritime activities. The clash between cultural heritage and rapid Blue Growth highlights a growing sense of disempowerment regarding the fair distribution of economic benefits.

Factor 1 is defined by eight participants in total (five men and three women): two recreational fisher, two fisher, a representative from an NGO, and three people from civil society.

Explaining 31% of total variance, this was by far the dominant discourse in TCL Cap de Creus.

Table 20 Item ranking TCL Cap de Creus Factor 1.

Factor 1 highlights participants' recognition of multiple opportunities to engage in environmental decision-making processes in Cap de Creus, including social movements, conferences, and workshops.

These participatory events provide spaces to discuss significant issues such as the development of a master plan for the region and proposals for offshore wind farms near an MPA. While participants appreciate being acknowledged and included in these processes, they emphasise that genuine consideration of their opinions and concerns is essential. Simply being heard is not enough—they seek tangible influence on decisions and policies. Participants who rely heavily on coastal resources for their livelihoods, particularly fishermen and divers, express a profound connection to their communities and the surrounding environment. This attachment is closely tied to the cultural heritage of Cap de Creus, to which they have historically contributed. Despite this involvement, many feel their traditional ways of life are increasingly under threat from new and expanding activities, such as the rising popularity of jet skis, which negatively impact the marine environment and disrupt fishing practices. The Factor also reveals critical views of the expanding “Blue Growth” tourism sector. Participants point out that the economic benefits generated by tourism are not fairly shared across the community, with many expressing concerns over precarious, poorly paid seasonal jobs that offer little stability or security. While there is some recognition that tourism can support vulnerable groups and provide employment opportunities, the rapid growth—often driven by external investors—has intensified pressures on local culture and resources. This growth has heightened tensions between the preservation of the traditional fishing sector and the expansion of other maritime industries, many of which operate with limited regulation. Fishers perceive an imbalance in regulatory enforcement: they face strict national regulations, while other sectors, such as tourism and marine leisure activities, continue to expand with fewer constraints. This perceived inequity contributes to perceptions of marginalization and displacement among fishing communities. Participants underscore the need for a more balanced approach that respects local heritage, protects environmental values, and ensures equitable distribution of benefits as the blue economy develops. Overall, Factor 1 reflects a nuanced tension between opportunities for civic participation, strong community and cultural ties, and concerns over social justice and sustainable development amidst ongoing Blue Growth in Cap de Creus.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

These results reflect a complex picture of Blue Justice in Cap de Creus. Participants generally feel empowered in terms of procedural justice—they have access to participatory events such as social movements, conferences, and workshops that allow them to engage in environmental decision-making processes. They also experience a degree of recognition, as their strong cultural and community ties, particularly among fishermen and divers, are acknowledged and valued. However, significant challenges remain regarding distributional justice. Participants perceive that the benefits of Blue Growth, especially in the tourism sector, are not shared fairly within the community. Economic gains tend to be unevenly distributed, with many local residents facing precarious and low-paid employment, while outside investors increasingly influence the sector. Moreover, there is a perceived imbalance in regulatory enforcement: traditional coastal livelihoods like fishing are heavily regulated, while newer maritime activities often expand with less oversight, leading to perceptions of marginalization and displacement. All of this highlights the need for more equitable policies that balance economic development with the protection of local communities and cultural heritage in Cap de Creus.

Summary interpretation: Factor 2 TCL Cap de Creus "Fair distribution but limited voice: Coastal communities feel recognised but disempowered in environmental decision-making"

Core themes: sentiment of participants who feel that the benefits of the environment and tourism are being fairly distributed, yet they remain excluded from the decision-making process. While they experience recognition of their cultural ties and connection to the sea, they express frustration at the lack of participation, with procedural disempowerment contrasting with their perceived fairness in resource distribution

Factor 2 is defined by six participants in total (five men and one women): two scuba divers, a recreational fisher, a representative from an NGO, and two people from civil society. SPAIN14 (a female from civil society) is negatively loading on that Factor. Explaining 21% of total variance, this was the second strongest discourse in TCL Cap de Creus.

Table 21 Item ranking TCL Cap de Creus Factor 2.

Those who score highly on this Factor agree that the impacts of environmental management decisions are distributed fairly and that the benefits of the tourism industry have been shared equitably across communities. However, they strongly disagree that they have the chance to participate in environmental decision-making, possibly due to their belief that their identity hinders their involvement in local decision-making. They feel a strong connection to their place and believe that the cultural ties between the community and the sea are acknowledged by society at large.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

Regarding justice, individuals associated with this Factor feel empowered in terms of distributional and recognition aspects. They perceive that the impacts of environmental management decisions are fairly shared and that the benefits of the tourism industry are equitably distributed across communities. Additionally, they believe their strong cultural connections to the sea and community are acknowledged by wider society. However, they experience significant disempowerment on procedural aspects, feeling that they lack meaningful opportunities to participate in environmental decision-making. This sense of exclusion may be linked to perceptions that their identity limits their influence in local governance, underscoring a critical gap in procedural justice within the blue economy context.

Summary interpretation: Factor 3 TCL Cap de Creus "Overlooked Heritage: Coastal communities feel procedurally empowered but struggle for cultural recognition"

Core themes: frustration at the lack of recognition of their historical and cultural ties to Cap de Creus, while emphasizing their empowerment in navigating local decision-making processes, despite their neutral views on resource distribution.

Factor 3 is defined by four participants in total (three men and one woman): two fisher, one scuba diver and a manager. Explaining 17% of total variance, this was the weakest discourse in TCL Cap de Creus.

Participants loading on Factor 3 argue that the historical and cultural links between Cap de Creus and the sea are not widely recognised by society. The community feels that their connection to the environment is not acknowledged, and that the government does not allocate resources in a way that enables them to live well along the coast. However, in cases of conflict, they are aware of whom to contact and that their identity does not hinder their participation in local decision-making processes.

In essence on Blue Justice dimensions

Individuals associated with this Factor feel empowered in procedural aspects of Blue Justice, as they know how to engage in local decision-making and do not perceive their identity as a barrier to participation. However, they experience a sense of disempowerment in recognitional aspects, feeling that their historical and cultural connections to Cap de Creus and the sea are insufficiently acknowledged by broader society. Their views on distributional justice are more neutral, reflecting uncertainty or ambivalence about whether resources and benefits are fairly allocated to support coastal livelihoods.

Table 22 Item ranking TCL Cap de Creus Factor 3.

Similarities and differences among perspectives in TCL Cap de Creus

All three Factors indicate that life in city centres is not superior – and we should mention here that Cap de Creus usually considers itself urban (Marty-Gastaldi et al. 2025), especially when comparing with other TCLs. They also strongly disagree that the Cap de Creus government distributes resources in a way that enables a good standard of living along the coast. Additionally, they would tend to disagree that all economic sectors are valued equally. While Factors 1 and 3 acknowledge the historical links, those who load on Factor 2 would strongly disagree. The perception that one's stakes in the environment are recognised is also important. People who scored high on Factors 1 and 3 rated this recognition positively, while those who scored high on Factor 2 felt more disempowered in this regard.

The key distinguishing Factors relate to perceptions of the benefits of Blue Growth, specifically within the tourism industry. While those who score highly on Factor 1 strongly disagree, Factor 3 rates this statement quite highly, and Factor 2 participants feel more neutral about the fair distribution of benefits of Blue Growth. Regarding meaningful participation in decision-making processes, individuals who score high on Factor 1 tend to feel empowered, while those who score high on Factor 2 tend to feel disempowered.

4.1.2 Baseline survey - Comparison between all TCLs

Across these Factors, several common themes and key differences emerge (Figure 4). Below is a comparison of these Factors based on their core themes:

Common Themes

Disempowerment in decision-making

Across many Factors in all TCLs, there is a recurring sense of disempowerment in environmental decision-making. Whether participants feel excluded at national, EU, or local levels, frustration stems from a lack of meaningful participation despite their connection to their environment and communities. Examples include TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 2's frustration with being "close to power but disempowered" or TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 1's critique of unfair conflict resolution in marine decision-making.

Fairness in resource distribution

Unequal distribution of resources and benefits is a prominent concern, particularly in sectors like tourism and Blue Growth. Factors in TCL Cap de Creus, TCL Træna, and TCL Åland express dissatisfaction with how benefits are distributed among coastal communities and industries. TCL Cap de Creus Factor 1, for instance, highlights concerns about the unequal distribution of benefits from tourism, while TCL Træna Factor 2 underscores issues of undervalued resources and unequal resource allocation in Arctic coastal regions.

Connection to place and culture

Participants consistently express a strong connection to place, environment, and cultural heritage. For example, TCL Åland Factor 2 and TCL Cap de Creus Factor 3 emphasise deep local ties and historical cultural practices. These connections are often linked to traditional livelihoods, such as fishing (Åland, Cap de Creus), and are seen as under threat from other industries, including tourism and Blue Growth initiatives.

Tension between tradition and modernity (Blue Growth)

Factors from TCLs like Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland), Træna (Norway), and Cap de Creus (Spain) illustrate a tension between preserving traditional livelihoods and accommodating modern economic growth initiatives like tourism and offshore wind farms. This tension frequently leads to concerns about fairness, with participants worrying that the growth of other sectors (e.g., tourism, aquaculture) is happening at the expense of traditional industries like fishing.

Procedural empowerment with limits

Many Factors (e.g., TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 1, TCL Cap de Creus Factor 1, TCL Træna Factor 2) show that participants feel they have procedural access to decision-making through workshops, social movements, or local engagement. However, this procedural involvement often does not translate into actual influence over decisions, particularly on higher levels. The gap between recognition and real influence is a common thread.

Julien Lebel, Nordlandsforskning AS, 2025

Figure 4 Similarities and differences across all six TCLs based on the Blue Q survey.

Key Differences between TCLs

Regional focus and sectoral concerns

TCL Træna Factors place specific emphasis on the peripheral Arctic region and challenges like ownership fears and transport issues that are distinct to Arctic communities. In contrast, TCL Cap de Creus Factors focus on the clash between tourism growth and traditional livelihoods in Cap de Creus. While both address Blue Growth, the regional contexts lead to different specific concerns (e.g., Arctic transport vs. coastal tourism).

Varying levels of procedural empowerment

While TCL Cap de Creus Factors feel some procedural empowerment, such as involvement in workshops and participatory processes, TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 1 and TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 2 highlight active local involvement but still feel deeply disempowered by the lack of meaningful impact from their participation. This shows a range of experiences, from limited procedural involvement to active, yet frustrated engagement.

Recognition vs. distributional justice

TCL Cap de Creus Factor 3 participants feel empowered in procedural decision-making but struggle with cultural recognition, whereas TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 1 and TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 2 focus more on the distribution of economic benefits and their perceived unfairness. TCL Cap de Creus Factor 2 sees procedural disempowerment despite perceived fairness in resource distribution, illustrating varying balances of power across recognition, procedural, and distributional justice.

Framing of Blue Growth and industrial development

TCL Eastern Limassol Region Factor 2 and TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factors approach Blue Growth with a critical perspective, noting government inconsistencies or project delays, while others like TCL Træna Factor 1 focus on the slow, sustainable growth model, resisting rapid industrial changes. The perception of Blue Growth ranges from support for employment opportunities (TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands Factor 2) to criticism of its uneven impact on traditional livelihoods (Træna, Cap de Creus).

Power dynamics and participation at higher levels

TCL Åland Factors highlight concerns over EU and national policies affecting local livelihoods, such as fishing rights, while TCL Træna Factors emphasise peripheral regions being left out of national decision-making. This contrasts with more localised issues seen in TCL Eastern Limassol Region and TCL Cap de Creus, where local engagement exists, but with varying degrees of influence.

Summary of themes and differences

Common themes: Disempowerment in decision-making, fairness concerns in resource distribution, strong place-based and cultural connections, tension between tradition and Blue Growth, and limited procedural empowerment.

Differences: Region-specific concerns (e.g., Arctic issues in Træna, tourism in Cap de Creus), varying experiences of procedural empowerment, focus on different justice dimensions (recognition vs. distribution), and differing perspectives on Blue Growth and industrial development.

4.2 Evaluation survey 2024/2025s

4.2.1 Evaluation survey results per TCL

Evaluation results in TCL Burgas (Bulgaria)

Qualitative analysis TCL Burgas

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Burgas

Recognitional justice

Participants reported that EmpowerUs activities in TCL Burgas have contributed to recognitional justice by fostering closer cooperation between project participants and local authorities, particularly the Municipality of Burgas. Respondents highlighted that the pilot activities not only helped accomplish goals with decision-makers but also promoted the region in alignment with municipal ambitions, such as the bid for becoming European Capital of Culture 2032. The pilot in TCL Burgas provided opportunities to combine modern and traditional communication tools, strengthening the connection between the municipality and its citizens, as one participant noted:

“With every new engagement and interaction with institutions and decision-makers you become better, the more exposure, the better – so the existence of a project per se contributed.”

Procedural justice

Procedural empowerment increased significantly due to expanded opportunities for project participants to engage with decision-makers. The establishment of working groups—such as the pioneering cycling group—created new structures for participation. Contacts with various municipal representatives led to greater influence in environmental matters, underlining the importance of maintaining dialogue to turn ideas into practice. These bottom-up processes are seen as having long-term benefits, reinforcing community voices in decision-making.

Distributional justice

While procedural and recognitional aspects improved, gains in distributional justice were more modest. Project activities opened discussions on improving mobility without private cars and developing wellbeing-oriented, creative, and educational opportunities. However, fairness in benefit distribution remains an area with limited change, partly due to structural constraints and the complexity of resource allocation.

Tailored empowerment program

Through the TEP and targeted activities, participants gained practical skills—from event planning and governance processes to ocean literacy and coastal management. The project’s collaborative format allowed the testing of locally relevant initiatives, such as new modes of citizen engagement with the local environment and educational opportunities, which both strengthened community engagement and contributed to broader sustainability goals.

Nature connectedness and understandings of sustainability

Sustainability was defined broadly, covering the responsible use of resources, financial viability of community initiatives, and balancing long-term environmental goals with daily practices. Nature connectedness was strengthened through activities that linked urban areas to surrounding lakes and natural areas, though participants noted the need for better infrastructure to facilitate access. This reflects a holistic sustainability understanding that blends ecological stewardship with social and economic resilience.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Burgas

Despite clear improvements, several challenges persist.

- **Recognitional justice:** Some actors were engaged too late in the process, limiting the full potential of mutual recognition and co-ownership. There is a perceived need to embed personal and ecological values more deeply into local culture.
- **Procedural justice:** Engagement increased, but sustaining participatory structures requires continuous funding and community mobilisation. Limited availability of volunteers and variable interest levels among the wider public risk weakening momentum.
- **Distributional justice:** Limited impact on fair distribution of benefits was noted. Suggestions include more expert input, stronger tourism linkages, and greater budget allocation for marine–community connections.
- **Structural challenges:** Instability in national politics, lack of sustainability education in schools, and time constraints from project deadlines restricted the scaling and consolidation of gains. One interviewee reflected:

“More time for our ideas... it would be great to have more time and resources to develop a more holistic strategy.”

Reflections using multi-level and power dimensions TCL Burgas

At the niche level (which deals with innovations and experimentations that foster interactions), the project stimulated grassroots innovations, such as the cycling working group, which could be replicated elsewhere. At the regime level (which encompasses dominant practices and rules that maintain stability in the community), municipal collaboration was strengthened, with procedural changes (e.g., working groups, participatory planning) embedding empowerment in local governance. At the landscape level (which focuses on social values, worldviews, institutions and market functions), broader societal and political instabilities, along with insufficient sustainability education, remain constraints that local projects alone cannot fully overcome.

In terms of power dimensions: Innovative power was enhanced through co-created pilot initiatives and the introduction of new participatory formats, generating fresh ideas for sustainable urban–nature linkages. Transformative power saw moderate growth, as the municipality integrated more citizen-led initiatives into its environmental and cultural agendas. Reinforceive power remains mixed—while trust and dialogue with municipal actors have improved, deeper cultural shifts towards ecological values are still needed.

Quantitative analysis TCL Burgas

The qualitative insights above are mirrored in the quantitative assessment, which confirms strong perceived gains in knowledge, resources, and willingness to act, while also highlighting areas—such as influence in environmental decision-making and fairness in resource distribution—where impacts were more limited or perceived as less relevant.

The interviewees in TCL Burgas highlight the strong impact of EmpowerUs on the empowerment of the local community in most of the aspects that are covered by the questionnaire (Figure 5). The answers emphasise that the project has strengthened the empowerment of the community by providing knowledge and resources, in addition to strengthening the willingness to take action, to a large extent in all these topics.

When it comes to aspects related to Blue Justice, the interviewees highlight the impact of the project on their connection to place and culture, which has been strengthened through project activities. Yet, the influence in environmental decision-making and fairness in resource distribution is characterised

by lower scores, with a significant share of interviewees answering “not relevant” in the latter topic. However, more interviewees are positive about the contribution of the project to strengthen the ability to balance tradition and modernity and to raise concerns to decision-makers.

Results from the questionnaire show a strong impact on aspects related to nature connectedness, although some respondents indicate that they already had a strong connection to nature before the project. Questions dealing with the TEP show that the interviewees consider there are many ideas to develop further the community in a sustainable way, but their perception is somewhat more nuanced regarding access to resources and willingness to put these ideas into practice.

Figure 5 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Burgas.

Juergen Leibel, Nordaforskning AS, 2025

Evaluation results in TCL Eastern Limassol Region (Cyprus)

Qualitative analysis TCL Eastern Limassol Region

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Eastern Limassol Region

Recognitional justice

Participation in EmpowerUs has strengthened mutual recognition between community members and some external actors, especially through inclusive workshops where all voices—officials, public authorities, and residents—could contribute in a respectful, non-confrontational setting. This shift in dialogue style, moving from “shouting and tension” to friendly, constructive exchanges, was identified as a key success in TCL Eastern Limassol Region. Residents reported that this approach made them feel heard and valued, and increased the likelihood that their concerns would be taken seriously. Residents do see the limitations however, since local environmental challenges, often overlooked by authorities, have been mapped and voiced, and have continued after these discussions. The project’s facilitation of direct connections to agencies like The Development Agency of Lemesos LTD (ANELEM) and Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI) has reinforced a sense that community perspectives can be recognised and integrated into planning. Nevertheless, recognition remains uneven at higher decision-making levels, where trust in government is still severely lacking (“We do not have any trust towards the government anymore”).

Procedural justice

EmpowerUs workshops increased procedural empowerment by offering opportunities for dialogue, collaborative strategy development, and engagement with public sector representatives. Participants gained greater confidence in communicating with decision-makers, understanding how to prepare and present their concerns effectively. The creation of a Strategic Community Plan was seen as a concrete outcome, giving structure to future engagement. More so, the maturation of one of the projects discussed during workshops to a point which is readily submittable by local authority reinforced this. The establishment of stronger networks with scientific experts further enhanced procedural capacity, enabling residents to follow up on issues like illegal dumping. However, the absence of actual decision-making authority for issues discussed in environmental impact assessment committees for example, remains a limitation. Follow-up actions after workshops were primarily with the community council, leading to a sense of discontinuity for other participants who might have wanted to be more involved.

Distributional justice

Through its participatory planning process and SWOT analysis, EmpowerUs ensured that diverse local stakeholders were equally involved in shaping sustainable development strategies. This was seen as a fairer and more interactive process than past top-down planning. The improved access to funding information—particularly via ANELEM—was a tangible distributional gain, as participants in the project now know both the sources of financial support and how to apply. Still, material resources remain insufficient. While the willingness to act has increased, many initiatives depend on external funding and sustained institutional backing.

Tailored empowerment program

TCL Eastern Limassol Region benefited from empowerment activities tailored to its local context, such as ocean literacy events, beach cleanups involving children, and strategic workshops integrating cultural and environmental concerns. These activities not only built skills but also fostered a stronger sense of agency—especially by showing that even in a landscape without iconic features like forests or rivers, underutilised local assets, can be highlighted through community activities and advocacy, and used as a basis for participation and local pride.

Nature connectedness and understandings of sustainability

Nature connection was reinforced through hands-on activities and awareness campaigns. Sustainability, as articulated by participants, centres on environmental protection, balanced development, and addressing the impacts of nearby industrial activities. Some residents proposed mild development (e.g., a small harbour) alongside conservation, indicating an interest in balanced, pragmatic sustainability rather than a preservationist approach.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Eastern Limassol Region

Despite the positive impacts of EmpowerUs, several challenges remain largely unchanged in the Eastern Limassol Region. These challenges cut across the Blue Justice dimensions, the TEP implementation, and nature connectedness:

- **Recognitional justice:** Recognition from national authorities remains weak; decades of neglect, lack of transparency, and unilateral decisions (e.g., marine aquaculture harbour) have eroded trust; relationships with certain agencies improved but no systematic authority engagement limits deeper recognitional change.
- **Procedural justice:** Procedural gains at niche level exist (workshops, council engagement) but structural constraints limit influence; EmpowerUs provided participation spaces but not formal decision-making power; workshops lacked ongoing follow-up to maintain momentum.
- **Distributional justice:** Financial resource gaps persist; community depends heavily on external funding; access to funding knowledge improved but actual funds remain scarce; industrial

pressures (waste, quarries, energy) continue shaping environmental risks and benefits beyond local control.

- **Nature connectedness and sustainability:** Although environmental awareness improved, industrial encroachment and cumulative impacts create a persistent sense of vulnerability (*“the future is grim”*). Sustainability visions are contested—some prioritise ecological protection, others economic development—leading to challenges in coordinating long-term strategies. Top-down decisions, such as the marine aquaculture harbour, sometimes reduce the perceived relevance of local environmental discussions (*“discussions on the importance of the environment feel irrelevant now... as if plastic straws were the real issue”*). Nonetheless, the increased awareness and engagement demonstrate a foundation upon which more coordinated and sustainable community-led actions could be built.

Multi-level perspective and power dimensions TCL Eastern Limassol Region

At the **niche level**, EmpowerUs successfully fostered innovative power through new partnerships (ANELEM, CMMI, community), participatory planning, and skills for constructive dialogue. These have created seeds for local change. At the **regime level**, transformative power remains limited; structural barriers—such as entrenched industrial development patterns and limited municipal autonomy—prevent scaling local initiatives into broader governance shifts. However, more municipal autonomy would not necessarily mean a focus on activities in line with sustainable development, as local authorities would more likely favour, for example, real estate. At the **landscape level**, persistent economic and industrial pressures reinforce existing trajectories, constraining transformative change and in some cases exercising **reinforce power** by maintaining dependence on external decisions and resources.

Quantitative analysis

The qualitative findings align closely with the results of the quantitative analysis, which further illustrates the areas where EmpowerUs has made the strongest contributions and where impacts have been more limited.

In TCL Eastern Limassol Region, the interviewees consider that EmpowerUs has contributed to a large extent to the empowerment of the local community, whether it is about accessing resources, getting knowledge to overcome challenges and strengthening willingness to take action (Figure 6). When it comes to the aspects related to Blue Justice, influence in environmental decision-making, connection to place and culture, and ability to balance tradition and modernity have been less impacted by the project than other topics. In the latter case, most of the respondents consider that the topic is not relevant, highlighting that it has not been a focus in project activities. However, data from the interviews show that EmpowerUs has positively influenced nature connectedness to a large extent. The respondents are also very positive regarding the TEP, although many of them are cautious about the availability of resources to put ideas into practice.

Figure 6 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Eastern Limassol Region.

Evaluation results in TCL Åland (Finland)

Qualitative analysis TCL Åland

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Åland

"The project has been valuable for building trust between the government and the local community; it is important to carry out activities in the field by involving people."

Recognitional justice TCL Åland

EmpowerUs has significantly strengthened local understanding of the complex governance structures in Åland, particularly around water ownership and ocean governance. By mapping these structures and making them visible, the project helped stakeholders better understand their own rights and responsibilities, enhancing their ability to participate in decision-making. This has also favoured mutual understanding between stakeholders with different interests. The involvement of small-scale commercial fishers—traditionally a group with limited policy influence—was a notable achievement, giving them a direct voice in discussions with decision-makers. Project outputs, including reports, not only documented local knowledge but also translated it into formats that could influence policies. This shift in visibility and representation reflects a marked improvement in recognitional justice, as local expertise was acknowledged as relevant and valuable.

Procedural justice TCL Åland

Procedural empowerment was strengthened through facilitated dialogue between diverse actors, including water owners, municipal officials, and fishers. The project created spaces—such as workshops and field trips—where perspectives could be exchanged, often for the first time, notably between decision-makers and small-scale commercial fishers. These interactions increased mutual understanding and trust, enabling more inclusive decision-making processes. By gathering knowledge and viewpoints in a consistent and formalised way, the project provided a foundation for policy engagement. It also created better opportunities for the integration of local knowledge in future policies, as some stakeholders emphasised that written outputs are more influential than oral

knowledge alone among decision-makers. However, challenges remain in influencing EU-level policies, which are perceived as disconnected from local realities.

Distributional justice TCL Åland

While EmpowerUs contributed indirectly to better resource distribution—e.g., by connecting fishers to museum-based initiatives that channel tourism revenue into local products—the overall impact on fairness in resource allocation was more modest. Respondents noted that the project helped to prioritise resource use and informed debates about fisheries and restoration, but structural issues (e.g., political budget priorities, large-scale aquaculture) remained largely untouched. Nonetheless, the emergence of follow-up projects suggests some positive momentum toward more equitable resource use.

Tailored empowerment program TCL Åland

The TEP in Åland supported practical actions for environmental protection, restoration, and fish stock conservation. Participants appreciated that EmpowerUs did not only produce reports but also directly supported local initiatives, reinforcing the willingness to implement new ideas. Capacity-building efforts improved the community's ability to engage with policy debates and apply for funding. Importantly, the TEP helped to “connect the dots” between well-being, biodiversity, and economic resilience—a linkage often missing from local policy debates.

Nature connectedness and understandings of sustainability TCL Åland

Nature connectedness was already strong in Åland, but EmpowerUs deepened understanding of how human well-being, economic activity, and ecosystem health are interdependent. Sustainability was understood as balancing development (e.g., tourism, fisheries) with environmental protection. Respondents stressed the need for long-term strategies for fisheries management, mass tourism regulation, and restoration of coastal waters. The project's emphasis on bottom-up approaches and cultural heritage reinforced these views, helping to frame sustainability as both an environmental and socio-cultural goal.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Åland

- **Recognitional justice:** Despite progress, some actors—especially those outside the core project network—remain underrepresented in decision-making. The complexity of multi-level governance still poses barriers to full recognition of local perspectives, particularly in EU policy contexts.
- **Procedural justice:** While dialogue improved locally, structural barriers limit influence at the regime and landscape levels. EU directives are often seen as ill-suited to Åland's context, and there is frustration over the limited ability to adapt them locally. Diverging local opinions (e.g., on herring fishing) also risk undermining procedural cohesion.
- **Distributional justice:** Even if mentioned in discussions during workshops, fairness in resource distribution was not a central focus of project activities, and impacts here were limited. Large-scale issues like wind power siting and industrial aquaculture remain politically and economically dominant, leaving small-scale fisheries in a vulnerable position. Political budget priorities and arbitrations within Åland's government often do not align with local conservation goals, reinforcing inequalities in access to resources. This highlights the importance of gathering relevant data and inputs from the communities to influence decision-making having impacts on sustainable development and fairness in resource distribution locally.

3. Reflections on multi-level and power dimensions TCL Åland

Multi-level changes TCL Åland

Niche level: EmpowerUs stimulated local initiatives in conservation and fisheries restoration, laying groundwork for longer-term projects.

Regime level: Trust-building and inclusion of new actors in governance discussions slightly shifted institutional norms, though diverging political priorities remain a barrier.

Landscape level: Influence is minimal due to misalignment between EU-level regulations and Åland's unique context, but the project improved the community's capacity to engage in higher-level policy debates.

Power dimensions TCL Åland

Innovative power: The project introduced new participatory methods, enabling fresh dialogues and problem framings between stakeholders who had limited (if not any) contact previously.

Transformative power: It fostered cross-sector alliances and empowered actors previously excluded from governance processes, such as small-scale fishers.

Reinforcive power: By strengthening existing stewardship values and traditional knowledge, EmpowerUs reinforced community-led conservation practices, though this did not yet translate into major structural change.

These qualitative findings are reflected in the quantitative results, which offer a broader view of where EmpowerUs has had the most impact in Åland.

Quantitative analysis TCL Åland

The survey data confirm strong perceived gains in willingness to take action and in knowledge about local governance and environmental conditions, while highlighting areas—such as influence in environmental decision-making and fairness in resource distribution—where impacts have been more limited or complex to address. Data from interviews in TCL Åland illustrate these trends in more detail (Figure 7): respondents considered their community to have been largely empowered through EmpowerUs activities, with willingness to take action being the dimension most positively affected. Many interviewees highlighted the valuable knowledge gained about local conditions, particularly regarding regulations and the water ownership system. EmpowerUs also moderately to largely supported connection to place and culture, balancing tradition and modernity, and raising concerns to decision-makers. However, the project's influence was more limited on environmental decision-making and fairness in resource distribution—topics considered important locally, but either complex to address or already partially influenced by participants' pre-existing roles. Regarding nature connectedness, the project particularly reinforced willingness to protect the environment, while implementation of the TEP positively influenced the willingness to put ideas into practice, although respondents noted some caution due to limited resources.

Figure 7 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Åland.

Evaluation results in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland)

Qualitative analysis TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Recognitional, procedural, and distributional justice TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Participants in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands report notable gains in both recognitional and procedural aspects of empowerment through EmpowerUs. On the recognitional side, they emphasised that the project reinforced cultural and linguistic identity, integrating the Irish language and local heritage into all activities. A trip to Scotland organised by EmpowerUs as part of the pilot, for example, allowed direct comparison with Scottish Gaelic preservation efforts, validating the community’s own approaches and instilling pride in their ongoing work. The project’s focus was seen as a strong acknowledgment of local values:

“Everything that is done has a basis in the language and the culture – the connection existed before EmpowerUs. The project emphasised the importance of it.”

Procedurally, EmpowerUs strengthened the ability to engage with and influence decision-making by providing resources, toolkits, and improved knowledge of governance structures. Activities such as presenting evidence-based proposals to decision-makers and networking with other community leaders were cited as critical procedural gains. The development of an EmpowerUs handbook on governance filled a previous gap in community resources, enabling more strategic engagement.

Distributional justice improvements were more modest but still visible. Some participants linked community ownership models—particularly for renewable energy and tourism facilities—to fairer benefit-sharing. However, there was a recognition that “more community ownership would help the community to share benefits more fairly,” signalling room for improvement.

Tailored empowerment program TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

The pilot activities in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands was seen as particularly effective in building capacity for larger projects. Many respondents highlighted increased confidence to take on ambitious initiatives, supported by tools like the solar pyranometer for evidence-based energy planning and financial analyses for tourism development. Networking opportunities—both formal and informal—were highly valued, with the Scotland trip repeatedly mentioned as a catalyst for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and morale boosting. The project also enabled the community to explore new strategic opportunities, such as community-owned tourist accommodation and retrofitting housing for energy efficiency, building on pre-existing energy masterplan work.

Nature connectedness and sustainability understandings TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Nature connectedness was already strong before EmpowerUs, but the project reinforced commitments to protecting the local environment and promoting sustainable practices. Understandings of sustainability were framed around balancing economic development with environmental protection, promoting community ownership of resources, and seeking long-term, resilient solutions. Examples included sustainable tourism, renewable energy projects, and traditional consumption practices (“going back to simpler ways of consuming and reusing things”).

The niche-level focus on sustainable tourism and decentralised working also reflects a broader systems view of sustainability, aligning with community resilience goals.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Despite gains, key barriers remain:

- **Procedural justice:**
 Financial and regulatory hurdles remain major barriers, especially in renewable energy and infrastructure projects.
 Difficulties include navigating planning systems, environmental protection rules, and securing funding.
 Conflict management and balancing competing interests (renewable energy, tourism, heritage conservation) remain unresolved despite EmpowerUs engagement tools.
- **Recognitional justice:**
 Much environmental and cultural work predated EmpowerUs; the project validated and supported it but “hasn’t contributed to anything new” in some areas.
 This highlights a strong pre-existing local empowerment base while showing that transformative change was less pronounced where empowerment was already high.
- **Distributional justice:**
 Challenges persist due to structural ownership patterns and benefit-sharing mechanisms.
 Participants call for greater community control of assets to address fairness in the distribution of benefits.

Reflections through multi-level and power dimensions TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

At the niche level, EmpowerUs reinforced ongoing initiatives like the community energy masterplan, sustainable tourism planning, and local language/culture integration. This helped strengthen innovative power by fostering new collaborations and enhancing technical capacity (e.g., renewable energy planning tools). At the landscape level, the project’s contribution was indirect, as larger socio-economic and cultural trends (e.g., heritage tourism growth, decentralisation of work) shaped opportunities and constraints.

In terms of the three power dimensions: Innovative power increased through tools, knowledge, and new project concepts. Transformative power improved in procedural engagement and advocacy capacity, though major regime shifts remain elusive. Reinforcive power was strengthened where

EmpowerUs built on pre-existing cultural and environmental stewardship, consolidating community identity and resilience.

These qualitative insights are broadly reflected in the quantitative findings, which further detail where EmpowerUs’ contributions were most strongly felt in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands and where impacts were more modest or perceived as less relevant.

Quantitative analysis TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands

Respondents from TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands mainly consider that their community has been empowered to a moderate extent through EmpowerUs activities (Figure 8). Willingness to take action is the dimension of empowerment where the project seems to have contributed the most. Many interviewees highlight that they gained useful insights and knowledge through project activities, especially during a field trip to Scotland, which has strengthened their willingness to take action.

Regarding Blue Justice aspects, most of the interviewees do not consider that EmpowerUs has contributed to a significant extent when it comes to influence in environmental decision-making, fairness in resource distribution, and ability to balance tradition and modernity. In many cases the respondents consider that these topics are not relevant regarding the activities they were involved in through the project. However, the project has contributed to a more significant extent to strengthening the connection to place and culture in the community, and many interviewees feel more confident about their ability to raise concerns to decision-makers as they gained more knowledge.

EmpowerUs influenced nature connectedness in the community to a limited extent as most of the respondents consider they already had a strong connection to nature before the project. Questions related to the TEP show that EmpowerUs has strengthened to a large extent the willingness to put ideas into practice in the community. The respondents are nevertheless more cautious regarding the availability of resources and the existence of various ideas to further stimulate sustainable development in their community.

Figure 8 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands.

Julien Lebel, Nord and Nordstaring AS, 2025

Evaluation results in TCL Træna (Norway)

Qualitative analysis TCL Træna

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Træna

Recognition justice TCL Træna

EmpowerUs contributed to raising awareness of Træna's unique cultural identity and sparked local reflection on community needs. Recognition has been strengthened through new partnerships (e.g., with Kunnskapsparken Helgeland (KPH) and NRI) and structured workshop formats that brought together actors who usually do not collaborate. This helped validate local culture while introducing fresh perspectives: "Holding on to the identity and culture that make us unique and special. I believe EmpowerUs is good at seeing and stating what is special about Træna."

However, recognition challenges persist for newcomers, who report being stereotyped and questioned about their long-term commitment, indicating that social inclusion remains partial.

Procedural justice TCL Træna

EmpowerUs offered platforms for structured dialogue and inclusive engagement, introducing methods like mixed-group workshops and collaborative goal-setting. These created space for residents to reflect collectively on challenges and long-term strategies. In Træna, access to political processes is already relatively open (e.g., 11 signatures can bring an issue to council), but the project's added value was in fostering more systematic thinking and providing tools for advocacy. Still, there was no strong link established between EmpowerUs and broader political decisions.

Distributional justice TCL Træna

The project had limited impact on redistributing structural resources from dominant sectors such as aquaculture or tourism. Its focus remained on community-driven initiatives—festivals, cultural hubs—rather than industry-level change. While this was perceived as fair in terms of targeting community benefit, it did not shift power balances or resource flows. Persistent inequalities in public service provision (e.g., unreliable kindergarten services, limited housing mobility for elderly) continue to shape local development capacity.

Tailored empowerment program TCL Træna

The TEP in Træna focused on enhancing strategic planning, grant-writing capacity, and multipurpose use of community spaces like Grendahuset. Participants appreciated the external facilitation and practical tools (e.g., funding application templates). Yet, progress was slowed by volunteer burnout, limited organisational continuity, and the lack of a dedicated coordinator. EmpowerUs' adaptability—offering support without overburdening limited capacity—was seen as a strength. For instance, a transport analysis has been carried out by EmpowerUs' researcher team to highlight both challenges and opportunities regarding the existing transport system, a major topic in Træna. The action space for the municipality and actionable recommendations to improve transport services have been described in this report, guiding for further actions in the community.

Nature connectedness and sustainability understanding TCL Træna

EmpowerUs moderately strengthened willingness to protect nature by linking it to creative, community-based uses (e.g., coastal gardens, sheep grazing). Sustainability in Træna is understood as a combination of long-term viability, intergenerational responsibility, innovation, and rootedness in local culture. However, many participants felt they already had a strong nature connection before the project, e.g., because sustainability is embedded in school curricula and daily practices.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Træna

Despite the positive impacts of EmpowerUs, several challenges remain largely unchanged in Træna. These challenges cut across the Blue Justice dimensions, the TEP implementation, and nature connectedness:

- **Recognitional justice:** Social divides persist; newcomers and seasonal residents feel partly excluded; “my project” mentalities limit broader collaboration; initiatives often tied to individuals rather than collective efforts.
- **Procedural justice:** Local procedural opportunities exist, but broader decision-making power (environmental regulation, industrial development) remains out of reach; workshops improved dialogue but did not connect to higher-level decision-making; absence of long-term coordinator risks loss of momentum.
- **Distributional justice:** No notable shift in benefits from dominant sectors (aquaculture, tourism, construction); local influence limited; basic public services lag behind mainland standards, constraining demographics and economic opportunity.
- **Nature connectedness and sustainability:** Strong personal connection to nature persists but has not translated into policy influence; environmental aspects deprioritised to avoid tension with economic development; structural pressures from industrial expansion remain unaltered.

Reflections across multi-level perspective and power dimensions TCL Træna

Regime Level: EmpowerUs did not alter the broader regime of economic development dominance over environmental protection, nor did it change structural service delivery inequalities. However, it encouraged local actors to demand parity with mainland standards in education and childcare.

Landscape Level: The tension between economic survival and environmental stewardship remains acute. While sustainability is embedded in education, industrial expansion (e.g., fish farms, hotel development) continues to overshadow ecological priorities.

Niche Level: At the community niche, the project strengthened strategic thinking, local cultural pride, and networking. It provided practical tools for small-scale innovation but was constrained by human and financial resources.

Power Dimensions TCL Træna

Innovative Power: Introduced new participatory methods and perspectives, fostering openness to change and sustainable tourism ideas.

Transformative Power: Limited—while it reframed discussions and built capacity, it did not shift the structural balance between development and environmental protection.

Reinforcive Power: Risk of reinforcing existing priorities (economic over environmental) through avoidance of contentious ecological debates, though this pragmatism was locally valued.

Quantitative analysis TCL Træna

The interviewees in TCL Træna consider that EmpowerUs has contributed to a moderate extent to the empowerment of the community (Figure 9). Project activities gave the opportunity to access different types of resources and knowledge, in addition to strengthening the willingness to take action. When it comes to Blue Justice aspects, the impacts of the project are rather limited according to the respondents on influence in environmental decision-making and fairness in resource distribution. Most of the interviewees highlight that these topics were not central in project activities in Træna, which can explain the high share of the answer “not relevant” in the questionnaire. However,

connection to place and culture and ability to raise concerns to decision-makers are topics where many interviewees consider that EmpowerUs contributed in a positive way.

The answers to the questions on nature connectedness show a limited impact of the project on this topic, as many interviewees emphasise that they already had a strong connection to nature before the project and are willing to focus on other dimensions of sustainability, particularly the economic aspects. When it comes to the TEP, the interviewees express a strong willingness to put ideas into practice in the community, although they are more cautious about the availability of resources due to population decline and lack of public and private fundings to support actions and services locally.

Figure 9 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Træna.

Ju'len Leibel, Nordlandforskning AS, 2025

Evaluation results in TCL Cap de Creus (Spain)

Qualitative analysis TCL Cap de Creus

Perceived improvements in empowerment TCL Cap de Creus

Recognitional, procedural, and distributional justice TCL Cap de Creus

Recognitional justice in Cap de Creus was strengthened primarily through the increased visibility and integration of local knowledge into decision-making. EmpowerUs provided a platform to raise awareness of existing regulations, share knowledge about the area’s culture and environment, and create spaces where different actors could express perspectives and experiences. Workshops were especially valued as inclusive arenas, enabling all participants to be heard and fostering mutual understanding. The project also helped link community discussions with decision-making processes beyond formal governmental channels, reinforcing a sense of agency. The role of the Natural Park’s new team was perceived positively, with improvements in transparency and cooperation.

Procedural justice saw advances in local networking and actor coordination. EmpowerUs facilitated inclusive governance discussions, encouraged representation of diverse interests, and connected actors who rarely interacted before. These connections enabled consensus-building and increased community cohesion around shared goals, even when definitions of fairness differed. However, some

respondents noted the persistence of bureaucratic barriers and the gap between local realities and decision-makers based outside the region.

Distributional justice improved through strengthened dialogue about equitable resource sharing. While challenges around long-term fairness remain, the project promoted a more collective vision for the region, ensuring that all voices could be heard when discussing resource allocation. EmpowerUs also made resources more visible, supporting transparency and accountability in their use.

Tailored empowerment program TCL Cap de Creus

EmpowerUs' tailored approach in Cap de Creus relied heavily on workshops, co-creation processes, and pilot activities like NaturCap – a digital sustainability initiative that promotes natural resource conservation and eco-friendly solutions, fostering responsible practices to protect biodiversity and support sustainable community development – which brought together diverse actors for dialogue and action. These activities were inclusive and grounded in the local culture, integrating economic, traditional, and ecological dimensions of sustainability. Knowledge-sharing was a recurring strength: stakeholders reported gaining new perspectives, learning about other sectors' challenges, and discovering practical solutions that connected local traditions with environmental protection.

Tailoring also meant building on existing environmental stewardship traditions. Many actors already had a strong commitment to protecting the area before the project; EmpowerUs consolidated these practices and offered new tools, such as environmental certifications for local businesses, sustainable tourism initiatives, and nature-based solutions.

Nature connectedness and sustainability understandings TCL Cap de Creus

Respondents generally reported a high pre-existing connection to nature, which EmpowerUs reinforced through collective activities and the integration of environmental themes in local economic initiatives (e.g., sustainable fishing, gastronomy linked to local products). The project's sustainability framing combined environmental and social dimensions, emphasising conservation, justice, community well-being, and the need to balance competing interests. Practical measures from community/tourism actors—like offering discounts to train travellers/public transport users or developing place-based tourism—linked environmental goals to tangible community benefits. However, there is still room to improve nature connectedness and overall sustainability, especially when it comes to mobility. This could include the promotion of shuttles to enter the natural park from all communities and thereby reduce car traffic, as well as limiting boats at the inlets of Cap de Creus and preventing the renting of boats without licenses.

Persistent challenges and unchanged aspects TCL Cap de Creus

Despite these advances, several structural and operational barriers remained:

- Bureaucratic hurdles and administrative complexity slowed down initiatives, making it difficult to act spontaneously and adapt processes to local contexts.
- Gaps between local communities and external decision-makers persisted, limiting the influence of local knowledge on higher-level governance. Decision-makers based outside the region were often unfamiliar with local conditions.
- Political will and time constraints were recurring bottlenecks, with limited capacity to move from ideas to implementation despite willingness.
- Inclusion issues were noted, particularly in ensuring that all community members—especially harder-to-reach groups—benefited equally from the project's outputs.
- Resource distribution and benefit-sharing did not always shift significantly; some felt existing inequalities in who gains from coastal resources persisted.
- Continuity concerns emerged around maintaining networks, momentum, and funding beyond the project's life.

- For nature connectedness, many said the project could not significantly deepen their existing connection to the environment, although the visitors are actually valuing conservation and cultural and natural heritage more highly than the locals (Gómez et al. 2025).
- Some sectors (tourism, nautical activities, land-based industries like vineyards) felt underrepresented, suggesting project activities and outreach could have been broader.

Reflections on multi-level empowerment changes TCL Cap de Creus

At the **regime level**, EmpowerUs fostered more inclusive coastal governance dialogues, challenged traditional top-down systems, and promoted recognition of diverse local perspectives. However, entrenched bureaucratic and political structures constrained transformative shifts, particularly in policy responsiveness.

At the **landscape level**, participants linked local challenges to broader EU-level and global issues—such as fishing regulations, food sovereignty, and sustainable tourism. They emphasised the need for stronger political coordination and commitment to address deeply rooted problems, including the prioritisation of economic growth over environmental protection.

At the **niche level**, the project successfully created protected collaborative spaces for experimentation (e.g., co-creation workshops, sustainable gastronomy events) and piloted practical solutions. These “safe spaces” allowed trust-building and the testing of novel ideas that could influence mainstream practices over time.

Reflections within the three power dimensions TCL Cap de Creus

Innovative power: The introduction of new practices—like sustainable business certifications, environmentally linked tourism incentives, and year-round mooring buoys—demonstrated creative solutions grounded in local resources and needs.

Transformative power: The project’s strongest contributions were in building relationships, shared visions, and consensus among diverse actors, laying the groundwork for more systemic change in governance.

Reinforcive power: EmpowerUs reinforced existing stewardship traditions and conservation ethics, while enhancing the visibility of these practices to wider audiences. However, some long-standing inequalities and institutional barriers remained largely intact.

Quantitative analysis TCL Cap de Creus

The positive impacts of EmpowerUs on the empowerment of TCL Cap de Creus is emphasised by the interviewees, especially when it comes to gaining knowledge to overcome challenges and strengthening the willingness to take action (Figure 10). Regarding access to resources, the respondents consider that the project impacted this aspect to a moderate extent.

Both connection to place and culture and nature connectedness have been particularly strengthened through project activities, as EmpowerUs impacted positively these aspects to a large extent. The interviewees consider nevertheless that the project had somewhat less impact on influence in environmental decision-making, fairness in resource distribution and ability to raise concerns to decision-makers. Some respondents emphasise that these topics were not central in project activities in the TCL. Answers to the questions dealing with the TEP show that the community has been particularly strengthened to pursue work and put new ideas into practice to ensure a sustainable development.

Figure 10 Quantitative evaluation in TCL Cap de Creus.

4.2.2 Evaluation survey – comparison between all TCLs

The evaluation survey across the six TCLs demonstrates that EmpowerUs has made a tangible contribution to strengthening perceptions of empowerment in coastal communities. Both the qualitative interviews and the quantitative data indicate that participants felt more capable of acting, better recognised in local processes, and more motivated to engage in collective problem-solving. At the same time, persistent structural barriers—particularly regarding influence on formal decision-making and availability and/or distribution of resources—limit the extent of change.

Changes in perception of empowerment

Procedural justice and strategies to mobilise

Procedural empowerment improved in nearly all sites. Participants reported new skills in preparing and presenting concerns, stronger community networks, and a greater capacity to engage decision-makers. The creation of local strategies and/or spaces for dialogue in some TCLs was valued as a concrete structure for future engagement. The pilots as part of the TEPs were central in strengthening strategies to mobilise.

The quantitative data supports this: *willingness to take action* stands out as the strongest empowerment dimension, scoring above 4 on average when considering all the TCLs together. This indicates that EmpowerUs not only raised awareness but also encouraged communities to translate discussions into potential action. *Access to resources and knowledge to overcome challenges* scored slightly lower (still significant, close to 4), reflecting both the valuable knowledge gained and the persistent difficulties in mobilising sufficient resources for implementation.

Recognitional justice and access to resources

Across all TCLs, participants felt better recognised as legitimate stakeholders in coastal governance compared to the baseline. EmpowerUs workshops, pilots and TEPs provided inclusive spaces where residents, fishers, farmers, NGOs, and local officials could meet as equals. In TCL Eastern Limassol Region and TCL Cap de Creus, this was described as a shift from tense, conflictual interactions toward constructive and respectful dialogue. However, it is an open question whether that kind of dialogue will continue in the future in a context of persistent challenges and diverging interests between actors.

Quantitative results (see Figure 11) confirm this trend: *connection to place and culture* is the Blue Justice aspect most strongly influenced by EmpowerUs, with an average score for all the TCLs together close to 4 (large extent contribution). The *ability to raise concerns to decision-makers* and the *ability to balance tradition and modernity* were also strengthened (scores above 3, moderate extent contribution). However, recognition was uneven at higher decision-making levels, where trust in government remained very low.

Distributional justice and willingness to act

Distributional justice showed the least improvement across the TCLs. While participatory planning was perceived as fairer than past top-down approaches, many interviewees stressed that actual distribution of resources, risks, and benefits remains outside their control. In TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands, TCL Træna, and TCL Eastern Limassol Region in particular, external industries—offshore wind, aquaculture, mining, and tourism—continued to dominate local development patterns. Many interviewees consider that the benefits deriving from these sectors are not necessarily reaching the community and not distributed in an equal way at the local level.

This perception is mirrored in the quantitative results: *fairness in resource distribution* and *influence in environmental decision-making* received the lowest average scores, and many respondents marked them as “not relevant” in their specific project activities. This underlines that while willingness to act has increased, structural distributional barriers remain largely unchanged.

Nature connectedness and sustainability

Nature connectedness was reinforced through hands-on activities, awareness campaigns, and discussions about sustainable futures. Yet many participants highlighted that their connection to nature was already strong before EmpowerUs, limiting the visible added impact of the project. Still, many respondents mentioned that the project strengthened their existing engagement/interest in protecting nature and valuing their local environment. It is also worth noting that this engagement/interest is closely related to the place attachment expressed by several participants in all the TCLs.

Quantitatively, nature connectedness scored on average above 3 (moderate contribution), confirming this picture of reinforcement rather than transformation. Willingness to put ideas into practice—an important aspect of empowerment—scored above 4, demonstrating that the TEPs helped communities envision practical pathways for action. Still, concerns about the *availability of resources* to implement ideas were voiced repeatedly, especially after the end of the project. As several participants noted, “*we have the ideas, but not yet the means.*”

Figure 11 Quantitative evaluation showing results for all the TCLs.

Shared patterns across the six TCLs

Several common trends emerge from combining the qualitative and quantitative evidence:

- **Empowerment gains were strongest in recognitional and procedural aspects**, particularly at the local level, while distributional justice remained weakest.
- **Willingness to act is the standout success**, consistently confirmed by both data types as the dimension most influenced by EmpowerUs.
- **Knowledge provision and capacity-building were highly valued**, though resource limitations remain a key constraint.
- **Trust in higher-level governance remains low**, with continued scepticism towards national and EU institutions. Still, in some TCLs the participants emphasised improvement regarding dialogue between local stakeholders and decision-makers (municipal/regional level).
- **Sustainability visions are pragmatic but contested**, with some communities prioritising conservation and others emphasising economic opportunity. The local context significantly influences the understanding of the concept of sustainability and the way to approach it, depending on existing challenges and perceived interests at the community level.

Divergences between the TCLs

While these patterns are broadly shared, important differences exist:

- **TCL Eastern Limassol Region and TCL Cap de Creus**: Strongest improvements in dialogue culture and mutual recognition, but trust in government remains low.
- **TCL Burgas and TCL Åland**: High gains in knowledge about regulations and ownership, but fairness in distribution remains marginal.
- **TCL Træna**: Community networking improved, but structural dependence on national industrial priorities persists.
- **TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands**: More moderate empowerment perceived, with limited relevance of Blue Justice dimensions beyond cultural connection.

Multi-level and power dimensions

At the **niche level**, EmpowerUs clearly strengthened *innovative power* by creating new networks, participatory strategies, and concrete empowerment tools. At the regime level, however,

transformative power was limited by entrenched governance and industrial structures. At the landscape level, broader economic and political pressures reinforced existing inequalities, exercising reinforcing power rather than supporting systemic change. It is important to note that such limited impacts at regime and landscape levels are not unexpected: given the three-year timeframe of the project, structural changes in governance systems or wider economic conditions are unlikely to manifest immediately. The more visible and lasting impacts therefore lie at the niche level, where EmpowerUs has shown most impact. However, many respondents emphasised that they expect further impacts from the project in the medium and long term, as the influence and results of project activities are not immediate. Moreover, cascading effects deriving from the project activities and initiatives can also be expected in the future with new ideas, methods and actions spreading in the community and favouring the engagement of more people and actors who were not necessarily involved in EmpowerUs.

5 Concluding discussion - lessons on empowerment from local to national level

EmpowerUs set out to strengthen the socio-economic empowerment of coastal communities through Tailored Empowerment Programs (TEPs). These programs aimed to build local capacities, enhance participation in governance, and foster more just and sustainable coastal transitions. Drawing on the evaluation of activities across six Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs), this concluding discussion reflects on the lessons learnt about overcoming institutional, financial, technical, and cultural barriers; on the role of the TEPs as well as tailored empowerment tools; and on the broader possibilities for social transition. It also contrasts the TCL-level findings with the results of a national ocean literacy survey, highlighting gaps between local lived experiences and national-level perceptions of sustainability in the six countries where the TCLs are located.

5.1 Lessons learnt in overcoming barriers

5.1.1 Institutional dimensions and dialogue within communities

One of the most consistent findings across the TCLs was the opening of new institutional pathways for engagement. Through workshops, working groups, and pilot initiatives, participants gained greater access to municipal representatives and local governance processes. These developments reflect improvements in procedural justice, as knowledge on how to access relevant administration departments and institutions, who to contact, and how to participate and influence decision-making got strengthened. In TCL Burgas (Bulgaria), for example, the establishment of a cycling working group created a new forum for dialogue that outlived the project's immediate activities.

At the same time, EmpowerUs highlighted that empowerment also depends on the quality of dialogue within communities themselves. The geographical position of coastal communities—at the interface of land and sea—brings together actors with diverse interests and knowledge: fishers, aquaculture operators, tourism entrepreneurs, cultural associations, and residents. Experiences from the TCLs show that these actors often share the same spaces but do not necessarily know each other well, which can create mistrust, reinforce unresolved conflicts, and block coordinated responses to common challenges.

By enabling workshops, study trips, seeding new networks and public events, EmpowerUs created arenas where local actors could meet, exchange ideas, and strengthen mutual understanding. These spaces stimulated inclusion and opened pathways to more united responses on complex issues. Participants emphasised that such dialogue needs continuity: without regular spaces for exchange, tensions resurface, and community cohesion weakens.

Yet, empowerment remained fragile when it comes to interacting with higher governance scales. National and EU-level decision-making processes continued to feel distant, abstract, and unresponsive from the community-level. Particularly in TCL Åland and TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands, respondents expressed frustration that while local access was possible, their ability to influence fisheries or offshore wind policies beyond their immediate context was negligible. This underlines the need for stronger institutional anchoring and long-term mechanisms that connect local dialogue and engagement with regional, national, and supranational governance.

5.1.2 Linking local voices and decision-makers

EmpowerUs highlighted the need for closer and more formalised contact between local actors and decision-makers, particularly to ensure that place-based knowledge informs policy. Across the TCLs, participants voiced frustration that national or EU policies often fail to recognise local realities, resulting in measures that inadvertently undermine livelihoods in coastal communities, such as fisheries restrictions or poorly planned industrial developments.

While the project improved procedural access to municipal actors, coordination across governance levels remains a major challenge. Residents often mistrust higher-level institutions and feel demotivated to engage with decision-makers who appear distant and disconnected from local contexts. EmpowerUs shows that empowerment requires not only community engagement, but also mechanisms for upward communication that ensure local knowledge can meaningfully influence regional, national, and EU-level policy agendas.

5.1.3 Access to resources and longevity of local actions

The distribution of resources and benefits continues to be one of the most significant barriers to empowerment. Across the TCLs, participants pointed to structural inequalities in how economic gains are shared—for instance, tourism profits concentrated in the hands of external investors in TCL Cap de Creus (Spain) and TCL Burgas (Bulgaria), or the prioritisation of offshore wind and aquaculture over traditional fisheries in TCL Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland) and TCL Åland (Finland). Such dynamics reinforced a widespread perception of unfairness and disempowerment in the distributional justice dimension.

EmpowerUs helped to partially counter these dynamics by providing limited but crucial resources in terms of expertise, organisational support, and seed funding. These inputs enabled communities to test new initiatives, build capacity, and generate visible outcomes—such as pilot infrastructures, educational workshops, and community networks. In TCL Eastern Limassol Region, for example, the project pilot has been linked to community funds and participatory planning of possible distribution of funds from the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF). Importantly, many participants across the TCLs reported that through the TEPs they were able to develop concrete ideas and plans for the future that extend beyond the life of the project. These included proposals for cultural heritage initiatives, sustainable mobility schemes, and new forms of coastal tourism or fisheries management.

Nevertheless, the uncertainty around access to resources remains a major challenge in all TCLs. Participants expressed concern about the lack of stable frameworks to carry these plans forward, noting that political priorities often shift toward short-term issues. Without secure financial and institutional backing, even well-developed plans risk stalling after the project ends. This creates a paradox: while scarcity has stimulated creativity and innovation, it also generates frustration, demotivation, and the risk of fragmentation when actors feel unable to turn ideas into practice.

Based on the feedback and concerns from project participants, one can emphasise that resources matter not only as direct financial inputs but also as guarantees of continuity. For local empowerment

to translate into long-term sustainability, community-driven plans and initiatives need to be supported by durable funding mechanisms and embedded in broader governance structures. Beyond financial resources, human resources are also determinant to carry out lasting actions with the engagement of motivated people willing to improve their communities. Yet, the capacities of certain actors and community members who are already involved in many different activities can be limited. Moreover, political and/or financial barriers and outmigration can negatively impact the willingness and capacity in taking actions at the community level.

5.1.4 Place-sensitive understandings of sustainability

A further lesson concerns the complexity of sustainability itself. EmpowerUs revealed that communities interpret the concept of “sustainability” in highly place-sensitive ways. For some, sustainability means securing fisheries and protecting cultural traditions; for others, it refers to balancing tourism development with environmental protection; for still others, it means ensuring intergenerational equity or reducing reliance on private cars. These differences show that participants have a different understanding of what sustainability means and encompasses. Therefore, it appears as a multi-dimensional term whose meaning shifts according to local challenges, experiences, and goals.

The project demonstrated the importance of creating spaces where diverse actors—including residents, business owners, scientists, and decision-makers—can debate what sustainability means in practice. In such discussions, the three classical dimensions (environmental, economic, social) were frequently reinterpreted and rebalanced according to community needs. EmpowerUs thus underscored the importance of dialogue not only as a means of cooperation, but also as a way of broadening the collective understanding of sustainability itself.

5.1.5 Cultural dimensions

EmpowerUs further demonstrated that cultural heritage and place attachment are vital drivers of empowerment, engagement for nature protection, and community development. Recognition of traditional practices, such as small-scale fisheries or coastal heritage events, contributed to strong community engagement, and for some participants reconsidering the value of local assets characterizing the community. Tailoring empowerment tools to respect and build upon cultural practices proved decisive: where TEPs aligned with local identity and traditions, empowerment was tangible and visible. Where they introduced agendas perceived as external, the impact was weaker.

5.1.6 TEPs and empowerment tools

TEPs provided the overarching framework for socio-economic empowerment in EmpowerUs, while locally implemented pilots operationalised these principles, making empowerment tangible through “learning by doing”. Tailoring in practice involved co-design with local academic leads and stakeholders, and adaptation to local contexts, languages, traditions, and challenges. Examples include cycling initiatives in Burgas, fisheries debates in Åland, tourism and heritage projects in Cap de Creus, activism in Connemara and the Aran Islands, and nature-based reconnection activities in Cyprus. Across TCLs, workshops, Q-method surveys, study trips, and ocean literacy activities were instrumental in linking pilot actions to the TEP framework.

Strengths of TEPs included improving recognitional and procedural justice by increasing visibility, voice, and inclusion; translating abstract empowerment concepts into concrete, place-based realities; and fostering local strategies and networks that support sustainable decision-making. EmpowerUs activities strengthened access to resources, fostered local willingness, and supported the development of strategies to mobilise change—such as fisheries plans, community-led tourism, or collaborative local initiatives—aligning local actions with the broader niche-to-niche regime transformation.

Limitations included limited impact on distributional justice, as structural inequalities persisted, and uncertainties about the sustainability of pilots and the broader TEP framework without institutional follow-up or dedicated resources.

The tailoring principle remains central to TEPs. Pilots became the main carriers of empowerment within the framework, demonstrating that meaningful change requires combining recognition, access, willingness, and actionable strategies to translate local learning into broader socio-ecological transformations that support Blue Justice.

5.1.7 Local TCL level and national perspectives on empowerment

The analyses presented in this report are based on responses from communities that are characterised by specific contexts, traditions and development paths. Therefore, we see merits in considering our results with empowerment data from the national level. To gain a broader view of society's perceptions of threats to the ocean, willingness to act to protect it and perceptions of empowerment in each country beyond the TCL, EmpowerUs teamed up with the wider Ocean Literacy Research Community³ to deliver the International Ocean & Society survey (McRuer et al. 2025). Results from these surveys provide the opportunity to identify common trends with what has been highlighted at the TCL level when it comes to the three dimensions of empowerment. Figure 12 summarises the national results for each country, in addition to calculating the “overall empowerment” as it has been done for each TCL.

Figure 12 Results from the national surveys in the six countries where the TCLs are located.

The national surveys, conducted with **5,425 respondents across six countries (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Norway, Spain)**, asked participants 30 standard questions on their understanding of and relationship with the ocean, and their willingness to care for it, following the methods described in McRuer et al. (2025). In addition, respondents were asked three questions related to their perceptions of empowerment to tackle personal and general community challenges (unrelated to ocean topics) —adapted from those asked at the TCL level—covering:

- their **knowledge** on how to overcome challenges,

³ <https://oceanliteracyresearch.com/>

- their **willingness** to participate in action, and
- their perceived **access to resources and tools**.

Further details are provided in the “Report on TCL Ocean Literacy Activities and Blue Justice Stories” (EmpowerUs Deliverable 6.3) and in the associated national policy briefs.

Results show that **knowledge** is the dimension with the strongest variation between countries. Ireland scored lowest (2.7), while Bulgaria and Cyprus were above average (close to 3.5). These differences underline the uneven availability of knowledge and cooperation mechanisms across countries and reflect the local-level finding that some communities were more successful than others in fostering cross-actor collaboration and knowledge exchange.

In contrast, **willingness to take action** received the highest share of positive answers across all countries, echoing TCL-level results. Scores were generally between 3 and 4, with Bulgaria, Spain, and Cyprus scoring highest (above 3.5), while Norway and Finland were lowest (closer to 3). These differences partly reflect the unequal density of existing networks and programs: in Nordic countries, sustainability has long been institutionalised, while in Southern regions the momentum around community action is growing more recently.

The lowest scores across all six countries were recorded in relation to **access to resources** (ranging between 2.5 and 3). Respondents often reported a lack of volunteers, political support, or funding to sustain action. These findings closely mirror the TCL-level results, where resource scarcity was consistently identified as the hardest barrier to overcome.

Overall, empowerment scores across the six countries gravitate around 3, though differences exist. Spain, Cyprus, and Bulgaria recorded the highest overall empowerment (≈ 3.25), while Finland and Ireland fell below 3. Importantly, these national-level averages provide a broad picture, but they mask the sharper conflicts and tensions evident at the TCL level.

This comparison therefore illustrates two key points: first, that national surveys capture generalised perceptions of empowerment along these dimensions, but risk overlooking the place-based justice concerns that communities experience daily; and second, that both levels reinforce each other in that improving empowerment is a continuous process, and needs a place and specific problem-based approach. While national results confirm broad willingness to act, local findings reveal the persistent barriers of fairness, resources, and recognition that must be addressed to turn this willingness into real transition. Bridging these perspectives will be essential for linking national strategies with the lived realities of coastal communities, for instance in delivering ocean literacy strategies that support empowering resource development that enables real changes to people’s lives and ocean health.

5.2 Synthesis and outlook

EmpowerUs shows that empowerment in coastal communities is multi-dimensional and uneven. It advanced recognitional and procedural justice by strengthening dialogue, visibility, and access, and contributed to broader understandings of sustainability by fostering local debates. However, distributional justice—fair access to resources and benefits—remains the greatest challenge. External factors such as political structures, demographic trends, and uneven public/private investments also affect local empowerment but lie beyond the project’s scope.

The TEPs demonstrate that tailoring is key: empowerment resonates when tools build on local cultures, languages, and traditions. Small-scale pilots stimulated learning, innovation, and community engagement, but without sustained resources, dialogue spaces, and institutional anchoring, these gains risk being temporary.

Future social transitions in coastal communities will depend on three conditions:

1. **Sustained dialogue spaces** that foster mutual understanding and cooperation among diverse actors.
2. **Formalised links to decision-makers**, ensuring that local voices and knowledge shape policies at higher levels.
3. **Stable resource frameworks**, so that community-driven initiatives can move beyond short-term projects toward long-term impact.

EmpowerUs has shown that empowerment is not a final outcome but a continuous process—one that requires constant negotiation, tailoring, and recognition of justice in all its dimensions. The Blue Q framework also offers practical guidance for future coastal transition initiatives and is integrated as supporting material in the WP5 Roadmap to Inclusive & Just Coastal Community Transitions (see EmpowerUs Deliverable 5.1), to assist both research and practice in scaling inclusive empowerment approaches. Beyond experimental application, the Blue Q framework and evaluation design provide concrete guidance for scaling EmpowerUs approaches. By embedding lessons learned into governance practices and future EU initiatives, EmpowerUs outputs support the longevity of empowerment and Blue Justice approaches. It also holds potential for uptake in Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs), the LEADER approach (community-led empowerment) promoted by the EU, and Horizon Europe contexts.

Beyond the project, this deliverable has utility for policymakers and practitioners working on coastal governance, social economy, and empowerment. Insights from this report could, for example, be integrated into training or capacity-building activities aimed at both stakeholders in coastal communities and policymakers working in relevant fields. The report emphasises both challenges and opportunities regarding sustainable development, dialogue, and empowerment in coastal communities where different actors are present and often have diverging interests and/or perceptions. As the report highlights obstacles but also methods and practices that succeeded in strengthening cooperation and improving participation and influence in decision-making, it could moreover constitute a useful tool for inspiration to develop/support efficient empowerment strategies in other coastal communities. Additionally, the findings should encourage policymakers to reflect upon their role in addressing issues in coastal communities, the impacts of policies designed at higher governance levels, and the opportunities to improve dialogue with actors in these communities to better capture local contexts, especially by including inputs coming from bottom-up approaches.

In this respect, the recently adopted European Ocean Pact provides a critical opportunity to advance these lessons. While the Pact acknowledges the importance of supporting coastal and island communities, the findings from EmpowerUs indicate that consultation alone is insufficient. Empowerment requires recognition, care, and relational values: strategies for the Blue Economy must therefore address not only economic and spatial planning, but also social dimensions, ensuring that communities experience policies as responsive rather than imposed.

EmpowerUs findings, as further elaborated in the project's *Policy Brief Coastal Transition Mechanisms: How to better integrate Europe's coastal communities and the Blue-Green Transition* (Ounanian et al. 2025 – Deliverable 5.3), provide concrete lessons for operationalising these principles. The Policy Brief highlights the importance of supporting bottom-up initiatives, aligning local priorities with EU-level strategies, and ensuring sustained institutional and financial backing—elements that are essential to transform engagement from symbolic consultation into genuine empowerment.

For the Ocean Pact and DG MARE, these lessons translate into three strategic considerations: establishing continuous and trusted channels for dialogue with coastal communities; integrating local knowledge into policy formulation at national and EU levels; and providing stable frameworks that allow community-driven initiatives to scale and endure. Implementing these approaches would strengthen the Ocean Pact’s potential to position coastal communities as equal partners in European ocean governance.

6 Literature

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7 Appendix

7.1 Questionnaire Evaluation survey

EmpowerUs WP3

Task 3.4 Evaluation of tailored empowerment programs – successes and failures of empowerment

Interview guidelines survey spring 2025

Thank you for taking the time to meet with us today. We have contacted you because you have been involved in some of the many activities in EmpowerUs and we are interested in your views. You may have been involved in one of our workshops, ocean literacy activities and/or pilot activities within EmpowerUs. The project is coming to an end this autumn and we would like to understand what you think has changed for you as a result of being part of the EmpowerUs project. And we would also like to hear your views on what has changed in your coastal community since/through/after the various EmpowerUs activities.

You may have taken part in a first round of evaluation we did at the start of the project (the Q-sorting interviews) - our aim there was to understand what you and others thought about your coastal community and your ability to influence progress and change in your community. Based on the results of this initial evaluation, we have developed this questionnaire to encourage you to reflect on any

changes you may have observed over the past 2.5 years of the project. We want to understand the potential impact of EmpowerUs and use the results to learn how other communities could be supported to thrive and face the challenges of blue injustice.

We will need between 60 and 90 minutes for the session. We will record the interviews and delete the recordings after transcription. After analysis, we will also delete the recordings (as you agreed in the **consent form**). If we want to quote you from the interview, we will ask for your permission.

We have prepared some questions that we would like you to answer on a scale from "not at all" to "to a very large extent" and we have more open-ended questions. It's important for us to mention that there are no right or wrong answers, but we are curious to hear your opinions, ideas and reflections. And we are also very open to your honest feedback and critical reflections on what the project has delivered, but also what could have been done differently.

Any questions before we get started?

Please take a moment and think back how you have been involved in EmpowerUs.

1. **Could you tell us in which activities and roles you have been involved in EmpowerUs? Now, we read some statements and ask you to rate them from "not at all" to "to a very large extent"; you also have the option to say this topic/statement has not been relevant for you within the project.**

General perception of empowerment changes

2. **With EmpowerUs, I have gained knowledge (in a broad way, such as organizing workshops, knowledge on topics such as the ocean, ...) to overcome challenges in my community.**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *Could you give examples of knowledge that you gained?*
2. *Is there any type of knowledge you would further need to overcome challenges in your community?*

3. **After EmpowerUs, I am (more) willing to take part in actions that make my community more sustainable.**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *Can you explain what sustainability means for you in 3 words?*
2. *Could you give examples of possible actions?*
3. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*

4. **With EmpowerUs, I have better access to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for me as individual or my community to thrive. With resources we broadly mean persons, assets, materials or capital, including human, mental, monetary, artificial and natural resources**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *What specific aspects or activities of the project contribute to this change?*
2. *What else would you need to have better access to resources? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Disempowerment in decision-making

5. **With EmpowerUs, I feel that I gained more influence in environmental decision-making.**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
2. *What would help you to gain more influence? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Fairness in resource distribution

6. **The EmpowerUs activities contributed to a fairer distribution of benefits from industries such as (mass)tourism, windfarms and/or aquaculture in my community**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
2. *What could help your community share (local) benefits more fairly? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Connection to place and culture

7. **With EmpowerUs, I have a stronger connection to the local culture and (social) environment**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *If not, what could be done to improve this?*
2. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
3. *What would help you to have a better connection to the local culture? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Connection to nature

8. **EmpowerUs had a positive influence on my connection to nature**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
2. *What would help you to have a better connection to nature? What could have been done differently in the project?*

9. **With EmpowerUs, I am more willing to protect (local) nature**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *What actions do you have in mind?*
2. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*

3. *What would help you to be more willing? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Tension between tradition and modernity

10. **With EmpowerUs, my community has become better to balance traditional ways of life with modern development**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *What role do you feel you play in this balance?*
2. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
3. *What would help you to support that balance more? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Procedural empowerment with limits

11. **With EmpowerUs, I am better prepared to raise my concerns to decision-makers in a more impactful way**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contribute to this?*
2. *What would help you to be better prepared? What could have been done differently in the project?*

Tailored Empowerment Program

12. **EmpowerUs supported our community to develop concrete ideas for future sustainable development of our community.**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

3. *In what way did the EmpowerUs activities contributed to this?*
4. *What would help your community to further develop these ideas? What could have been done differently in the project?*

13. **My community has the resources, knowledge and skills to put these ideas into practice beyond the EmpowerUs project**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *Please specify*

14. **In my community there is the willingness to put these ideas into practice beyond the EmpowerUs project**

Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	Not relevant

1. *What could strengthen this willingness? Where do you see barriers?*
2. *What would further support your community?*

15. Any additional aspects you would like to mention?

7.2 Codebook NVivo Evaluation survey

NVIVO code descriptions

Code name	Description
Blue Justice - recognitional justice BJ_RJ	Code text passages where communities express awareness, understanding, or knowledge about how to access institutions, engage with governance structures, or navigate administrative systems.
Blue Justice_distributinal justice BJ_DJ	Distributional Justice – Fair Outcomes: distributional justice is about their ability to rely on fair resolution. Code text passages where communities discuss their ability to receive fair outcomes, benefits, or resources, or express trust (or lack thereof) in the fairness of how decisions and resources are distributed.
Blue Justice_procedural justice BJ_PJ	Access to decision-making: Procedural justice is about their ability to access (rather than just know about) decision-making processes - Code text passages where communities describe their ability or inability to actively participate in, influence, or access decision-making processes, beyond just knowing about them.
Definition Sustainability Sust	Code any answers to Question 3 that answer to the question: define what sustainability means for you
Empowerment Knowledge Emp_K	Code text passages where individuals or communities refer to knowledge that helps address local challenges — including practical, scientific, or organizational knowledge (e.g., about the environment, like the ocean, or through activities such as organizing workshops or sharing expertise).
Empowerment Strategies to mobilise Emp_St	Code text passages where individuals or communities describe approaches, plans, tactics, or methods they use (or could use) to activate, coordinate, or make use of resources and institutions to achieve their community goals.
Empowerment Willingness to mobilise Emp_W	Code text passages where individuals or communities' express motivation, intention, commitment, or readiness to use available resources and institutions to achieve specific goals — regardless of whether they already have access or strategies in place.
Empowerment_Access Emp_A	Access to resources and institutions: Code text passages where individuals or communities describe their ability or inability to access or benefit from resources (broadly understood as persons, assets, materials, or capital — including human, mental, financial, artificial, and natural resources) or from institutions such as public services, government agencies, or legal bodies.
General failures G_fail	Code text passages that describe challenges, obstacles, or negative outcomes where individuals or communities were unable to gain capacity — for example due to limited access to resources and institutions, ineffective or missing strategies to mobilise them, or lack of willingness or motivation to act.
General successes G_suc	Code text passages that describe positive outcomes, effective practices, or examples where individuals or communities successfully gained capacity — specifically through

	improved access to resources and institutions, effective strategies to mobilise them, or strong willingness and motivation to act.
Multi-level _niche MLP_N	Code text passages referring to local or community spaces where (radical) innovation and experimentation take place, fostering collaborative interactions among actors to support new products or process innovation
Multi-level regime MLP_r	Regime (Meso) Level – Dominant Practices and Structures: Code text passages describing dominant practices, established rules, standard technologies, or institutional structures that maintain stability and reinforce existing socio-technical systems.
Multi-level landscape MLP_l	Landscape (Macro) Level – Socio-Technical Context: Code text passages referring to the broad socio-technical environment, including intangible elements such as social values, political beliefs, and worldviews, as well as tangible aspects like institutions, built environment, market functions (e.g., prices, costs, trade patterns, incomes) - EU regulations etc.
Power_innovative P_I	Innovative power: Code text passages where actors demonstrate the ability to generate new resources—physical, human, monetary, or mental—that challenge or disrupt existing power structures, emphasizing visible, collective actions and the creation of impactful innovations that shift power relations.
Power_reinforcive P_R	Reinforcive Power: Code text passages where individuals or groups exercise power to maintain, reproduce, or uphold existing structures and institutions, emphasizing human agency and intentional actions behind sustaining power relations—even when power seems systemic or automated.
Power_transformative P_T	Transformative power: Code text passages where actors create or significantly modify structures and institutions (e.g., legal frameworks, economic systems), challenging and reshaping existing systems through recombination or reinvention, leading to meaningful and sustained change often in combination with reinforcing power.
Other O	Code all other interesting text passages that might be relevant but do not fit into one of the other categories.